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Science communication & science diplomacy can serve as a bridge between Islamic nations fostering collaborations in areas of mutual interest, enhancing diplomatic relations and promoting peace and stability.

OIC Ministerial Standing Committee on
Scientific and Technological Cooperation

COMSTECH

Ministry of Foreign Affairs,
Government of Pakistan

MoFA

Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy

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Message of Secretary Ministry of Foreign Affairs

I am honored to contribute to the second issue of the *Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy (JSC&D)*, a publication that plays a vital role in promoting the integration of science and diplomacy to address the most pressing challenges faced by the OIC countries and the wider global community. As the Director General of Science Diplomacy at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, I have witnessed firsthand the importance of fostering cooperation between the scientific and diplomatic communities to tackle global challenges effectively. This journal exemplifies how science diplomacy can bridge the gap between scientific innovation and diplomatic efforts, ensuring that scientific knowledge translates into tangible benefits for all.

This issue of the journal brings forth compelling discussions on the role of science communication in shaping public perception, enhancing global cooperation, and fostering innovation. The contributions cover a broad range of critical topics, from the promotion of science literacy through media education to leveraging science communication for technological advancement and innovation within science and technology parks. These topics are of particular importance in the context of the OIC member states, where cultural, socio-economic, and political contexts often present unique challenges in disseminating scientific information and implementing effective policies.

I would like to take this opportunity to extend my deepest thanks to the authors for their valuable contributions and to the editorial team for their hard work in bringing this second issue of the journal to fruition. It is my hope that this journal continues to serve as a platform for dialogue, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among scientists, diplomats, and policymakers across the OIC region and the world.

In conclusion, I encourage all readers, researchers, and stakeholders to continue engaging with the *Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy*, as it remains a vital resource for shaping the future of science, communication, and diplomacy.

Ambassador Ms. Amna Baloch
Secretary, Ministry of Foreign Affairs
Government of Pakistan

Message of Patron-in-Chief

I am pleased to extend my sincere congratulations to the editorial team, contributors, and readers of the Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy (JSC&D) on the publication of its 2nd issue. The Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy is an essential platform for exploring the intersection of science and diplomacy in the OIC region. This second issue further strengthens the journal's role in advancing global scientific collaboration and promoting the dissemination of critical knowledge in response to the challenges faced by our societies. Together, we can leverage the power of science diplomacy to drive positive change for the betterment of humanity.

The field of science communication is integral in the contemporary world, where the relationship between science, technology, and diplomacy continues to evolve rapidly. As the world faces numerous global challenges, including climate change, public health crises, and geopolitical tensions, the importance of science diplomacy has never been clearer. This journal serves as a vital conduit for the exchange of ideas and strategies, enabling countries to collaborate on these global challenges in a coordinated and strategic manner.

In this issue, we see an excellent range of articles that address pertinent issues within the realm of science communication and diplomacy. Topics such as the enhancement of global cooperation in scientific research, strategies for promoting science literacy, and the urgent need for science communication in Pakistan's technological development highlight the vital intersections between science, communication, and diplomacy. This publication serves as a reminder of the immense potential that science diplomacy holds for shaping international policies, advancing sustainable development, and addressing health disparities.

As we continue to build scientific and diplomatic bridges within the OIC region and beyond, I encourage all stakeholders—scientists, diplomats, policymakers, and researchers—to utilize the journal's offerings as a valuable resource in the collective effort to address global challenges. The power of science and diplomacy working together for the betterment of humanity is immense, and the JSC&D will undoubtedly play an important role in this effort.

I commend the editorial board and the authors for their outstanding contributions to the second issue of the journal, and I look forward to the continued success and impact of this valuable publication.

Prof. Dr. M. Iqbal Choudhary
Mustafa (pbuh) Prize Laureate, H.I., S.I., T.I.
Coordinator General, OIC-COMSTECH

Message of Editor-in-Chief

As the Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Science Communication & Diplomacy, it is my distinct pleasure to present the second issue of this important journal, which continues to serve as a crucial platform for disseminating research and insights on the intersection of science, communication, and diplomacy. The journal aims to connect scientists, researchers, policymakers, and diplomats within the OIC countries, enabling them to work together to achieve shared goals of scientific advancement and sustainable development.

The articles presented in this issue address a diverse array of topics, each critical to the progress of science communication and diplomacy. From exploring the challenges and opportunities of science communication in the Muslim world to examining the need for science diplomacy in addressing complex issues such as vaccine and global health, this issue reflects the ongoing efforts to integrate scientific knowledge into diplomatic strategies for the benefit of humanity.

A significant aspect of this issue is the emphasis on the role of science communication in enhancing public health, technological development, and innovation within the OIC member states. The importance of effective science communication strategies is underscored as a means to empower communities, reduce disparities, and foster cooperation in tackling pressing global challenges, particularly those related to climate change, health crises, and economic development.

The articles also highlight the role of science communication in driving innovation, particularly in developing countries where there is an increasing need to bridge the gap between research and its practical applications. The contributions offer valuable recommendations for fostering innovation and entrepreneurship through better communication strategies, ensuring that the benefits of science and technology are accessible to all.

Science diplomacy is an evolving field with lot of potential, and as such, it is crucial that we continue to explore and document new approaches and strategies that foster international cooperation in scientific research, development, and policy-making. This issue contributes significantly to the growing body of literature on science diplomacy, and I am confident that it will serve as a valuable resource for all those working in the this upcoming field of science communication, diplomacy, and international cooperation.

I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to the esteemed authors for their contributions, and to the dedicated editorial team for their tireless efforts in bringing this journal to life on this important topic. The second issue of the JSC&D is a testament to our shared commitment to the advancement of science and diplomacy for the betterment of our societies and the world.

Prof. Dr. Syed Javaid Khurshid
Consultant, Science Communication & Diplomacy OIC-COMSTECH

Science Communication in the Muslim World: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

The Muslim world, comprising over 1.8 billion people, has a rich history of scientific achievements but lags in effective scientific communication. Despite initiatives to communicate science, the region faces significant challenges, including low investment in research and development, limited global research output, and low science literacy. The article highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to address these challenges, emphasizing the importance of promoting science education, critical thinking, and inquiry-based learning. It also stresses the need for a robust science media ecosystem, science-focused media outlets, and science journalism training. Leveraging digital technologies and multimedia mechanisms can also enhance science communication. International collaborations and global dialogue are essential to diversify science communication strategies and engage the global scientific community. By implementing these measures, the Muslim world can enhance science communication, drive progress in various fields, and contribute to socio-economic development and international competitiveness. The article concludes by emphasizing the need for a national and regional science communication strategy to address the challenges and opportunities in science communication in the Muslim world.

Keywords: Muslim World, Science Communication, Socio-economic Development, Science Education

Introduction

Science popularization depends upon, how science is communicated to the common masses, what's flexible medium or language used to disseminate the message, how it's effective and easy to understand, whether we are on the spot regarding the targeted audience or not, what are the objectives to achieve, means lots of questions need answers when it comes to have an effective science communication.

The Muslim world, comprising over 1.8 billion people and is home to a rich history of scientific achievements. However, in recent times, when global outreach in every sphere enhanced to the highest level, the world turned into a global village, and all sorts of information is at the figure tips - but unfortunately, the Islamic world including Pakistan, is lagging behind in effective and result oriented science communication.

Several initiatives were taken across developing regions, especially in several Islamic countries, to communicate science effectively, but comparatively, it's not much of

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an impact. The situation compels us to prioritize science at every level in our everyday life, especially in the private sector, and make it inevitable to exchange scientific knowledge, research, innovations, discoveries, technologies, and advancements among each other within societies, bilaterally among nations and multilaterally across different regions.

Why the Muslim World Lags Behind in Science Communication?

Concerning the different publications, the Muslim world's majority spend a meager 0.3 percent of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on Research and Development (R&D), the Islamic world accounts for 2.5 percent of global research output, having 1.3 percent contributions in terms of scientific publications, women account for 35% of researchers, having low international collaborations as only 10 percent of publications involving international Co-authors while only 40% of adults across Muslim nations have below-average science literacy.

The language barrier has so serious implications that only Arabic, the primary language of many Muslim-majority countries, has a limited number of scientific publications, say only 1.1% of the global total while the majority of nations have meager contributions in translating scientific knowledge into their own national or local languages.

Science literacy, is another grave issue, as different surveys unveil that among every 10 Muslim countries, only 22 percent of the respondents had a basic understanding of science and technology while scientific education across Muslim regions faces lots of hurdles and acute challenges. Majority of Muslim countries have dwindling economic situations, have a lack of will or focus to move towards science and technology, they lack properly trained scientific teaching staff in schools, having meager financial resources, equipment and low access to the latest technologies due to the western world's monopoly.

These are the very reasons that the science communication gap is as serious as 70 percent of the Muslims have never heard about any Muslim scientist or inventor or discoverer in their whole life. It's all because in Muslim world, digital, print and electronic media science coverage is extremely limited, with only 1.5% of news stories are generated on average. Majority of the Muslim world rely on Western science news sources rather developing their own science media resources.

In the Islamic world, 60% of science stories focused on technology and its applications, rather than basic science, only 10 percent countries have dedicated science media outlets, 20% of media outlets have dedicated science sections on their websites, 70% of Muslim-world media outlets publish science stories less than once a week, 80% of science stories in Muslim-world media are sourced from Western news media while only 30% of science stories focused on local research or issues. Only 20% of science stories in Muslim-world media include images, videos, or info-graphics. Specialized science journalism training is only available to 10 percent of the journalists across Islamic media while such media outlets only encourage 15 percent of the audience to engage in science stories.

Science education is not much popularized among students, mainly due to no libraries, laboratories, equipment, or resources, especially in schools. So such a situation severely impacts every institution including the media but the overall media landscape as well, when journalists don't have a scientific education, they are least interested in science reporting and similarly majority don't prefer science editorially, what's happening in majority media entities.

The following strategies will enhance readability. Some recommendations could be more specific. For t specific actions should be taken to compel legislators to support science education? Some of the Strategies as following can be suggested as for Improving Science Communication

1. Revitalizing Knowledge-Sharing Traditions:
2. Developing a Robust Science Media Ecosystem:
3. Leveraging Digital Technologies:
4. Enhancing Collaboration and Communication:
5. Establishing Science Communication Platforms:
6. Recognizing and Rewarding Excellence:
7. Developing National and Regional Strategies:
8. Fostering International Collaborations:

What's Inevitable to be Done?

We have to address the main challenges facing science communication in Pakistan and across the Islamic world. It's imperative to revitalize the golden Islamic tradition of knowledge-sharing and curiosity. This can be achieved, first by compelling legislators, policymakers, bureaucracy and institutions to willingly work for science and technology enhancement along with promoting science education, critical thinking, and inquiry-based learning across our educational institutions at all levels from grassroots level schools to higher education like colleges and universities.

Secondly, and extremely important, developing a robust science media ecosystem with science reporting as a permanent feature, and editorial support, encourages broadcast and print media to have dedicated time and space with robust science-related stories, programs, public service messages, articles, features, compelling science and tech companies and industry to advertise such media initiatives, because media can't move without financial resources.

Emphasizing on science-focused media outlets is necessary and for that matter, we have to encourage science mentorship, and knowledge sharing, and induct science news editors (with science journalistic backgrounds) in media organizations. Make the media coverage of scientific breakthroughs, innovations, inventions, and discoveries a regular feature. For this scientists, scientific societies, organizations, research centers, and academia have to be flexible in sharing key knowledge, research, and data with journalists.

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Science journalists' training and capacity building is inevitable to have sound scientific knowledge, understanding of basic scientific principles and methods, connections with researchers, experts, and institutions to seek accurate information, have critical thinking, and analytical skills, can question, evaluate evidence, and verify information to avoid misinformation.

For a science journalist, staying updated on scientific developments and communication techniques is also necessary. It's also very important to place scientific findings in a broader context and highlight implications as well. Storytelling techniques are absolutely heart-touching and compelling the masses to engage, so use attractive visuals, photos, and narratives to make science easy to understand. Include the unheard voices and ignored segments of society in science stories.

Thirdly, It would be vital to leverage digital technologies and multimedia mechanisms, such as social media, podcasts, online videos, spaces, and webinars, to reach a wider audience, and make science communication more accessible and engaging.

Fourthly, encourage scientists, researchers, and even journalists to collaborate, translate, and effectively communicate complex scientific ideas and research findings to the media outlets, journalists, and even directly to the general public, in extremely simplistic form, preferably through localized content, remove all language barriers, avoid jargons and sci-tech complex terminologies to effectively communicate scientific knowledge to a broader audience.

Fifthly, establish science communication platforms, such as regular science debates among scientists, policymakers, legislators, journalists, academicians, and students, conducting science festivals, exhibitions, public lectures, and online forums regularly, to engage the public. Such platforms will provide opportunities for scientists to share their research findings, knowledge, and wisdom while also giving opportunities to the journalists and the public to ask questions and seek clarifications.

Sixthly, recognize and reward the outstanding scientists, science communicators, journalists, policy makers and others, motivating others to follow in their footsteps. This could be done through awards, fellowships, and recognition programs at the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) Committee on Science and Technology (COMSTECH).

Seventhly, develop national and regional (at OIC COMSTECH level) science communication strategy, outlining clear goals, objectives, and action plans. Such a strategy should be developed in consultation with stakeholders from government, media, academia, industry, and think tanks.

Last but not the least, fostering international collaborations, and permanent global dialogue between scientists, journalists, and policymakers is important to diversify science communication strategies and engage world scientific community so that third-world science enthusiasts can have participation and partnerships with global science communication initiatives, exchange the best practices and expertise, collaborate on science communication projects and research, while establish a joint mechanism to

exchange science communicators, journalists, academia and researchers to enhance their skills, expertise, knowledge, and outreach.

By effectively implementing such measures, we can enhance science communication across the Muslim world including Pakistan, and drive progress in various fields, from healthcare, and agriculture to energy, water, and environment to climate change, ultimately contributing to socio-economic development and global competitiveness. It can be adopting following strategies;

1. National science communication policies: Advocate for policy development.
2. Science journalism training: Provide specialized training programs.
3. Public engagement: Organize science festivals, exhibitions and public lectures.
4. Incentives: Offer awards, fellowships and recognition programs.

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Enhancing Global Cooperation in Scientific Research, Development, and Policy Making Through Science Diplomacy: Challenges and Strategies

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Abstract

Science diplomacy is vital in fostering international collaboration in scientific research and policy-making. This framework aims to facilitate cooperation, knowledge sharing, and capacity building, ultimately informing policy-making with scientific evidence. Focusing on global challenges and emerging technologies, this initiative promotes joint research projects, scientific workshops, policy dialogues, and capacity building programs. By leveraging scientific cooperation, nations can address global challenges, promote mutual understanding, and drive innovation. This approach ensures data-driven decision making, policy coherence, and alignment with global agendas like the SDGs and Paris Agreement.

Keywords: Science Diplomacy, COP 28, COP-29, COVID-19, Global cooperation, scientific research, SDGs, Policy Making

Introduction

Science diplomacy plays a crucial role in facilitating international collaboration in scientific research and policy-making, necessitating strong synergy between stakeholders from the scientific community and foreign policy spheres. By harnessing the power of scientific cooperation, nations can effectively address pressing global challenges, such as climate change, pandemics, and sustainable development, that transcend borders and require collective action. Science diplomacy fosters mutual understanding, trust, and respect among nations, enabling them to leverage each other's strengths, share knowledge, and drive innovation. This framework seeks to bridge the gap between science and policy by facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, and capacity building, ultimately ensuring that policy decisions are informed by robust scientific evidence. By doing so, science diplomacy can help nations to navigate complex global issues, promote peaceful resolution of conflicts, and drive progress towards achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The primary goal of science diplomacy is to foster international relations and collaboration in groundbreaking scientific research, prioritizing global challenges and cutting-edge technologies. This endeavor aims to facilitate the exchange of knowledge,

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enhance capacity building, and enable technology transfer, ultimately bridging the gap between nations and promoting collective progress. By doing so, science diplomacy seeks to empower policy-makers with reliable scientific evidence, ensuring data-driven decision-making and strengthening international partnerships, cooperation, and diplomacy. Through this framework, nations can collectively address pressing global issues, drive innovation, and promote peaceful resolution of conflicts, thereby advancing the global community's well-being and prosperity. Nations and cultures have long built relationships based on science to build a key element of trust. Another train of thought is that, since scientific practice values rationality, transparency, and universality, these core values can, in turn, help promote good governance and a free exchange of ideas across people of all nationalities and cultural or religious backgrounds. Science itself knows no boundaries and scientific knowledge is universal.

Today, nations are increasingly placing scientific attachés in their overseas embassies. Diplomacy may help lay the foundation for the next multi-national science projects. Scientific cooperation can begin with the explicit intention of improving relations between nations and achieving a path for mutual prosperity.

In the context of addressing global challenges and promoting sustainable development, science diplomacy plays a vital role in fostering international collaboration and innovation. The primary goal of science diplomacy is to foster international relations and collaboration in groundbreaking scientific research, prioritizing global challenges and cutting-edge technologies. This endeavor aims to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, enhance capacity building, and enable technology transfer, ultimately bridging the gap between nations and promoting collective progress.

- Science in diplomacy is about the use of scientific advice for foreign policy decision-making. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) of the United Nations is an excellent example. Established in 1988, the IPCC brings together the latest scientific advice on climate change.
- COP 28 (2023): The 28th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) was held in the United Arab Emirates. Science diplomacy will play a crucial role in informing policy-making and facilitating collaboration on climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies.
- COP 29 (2024): The 29th Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC was held in Egypt. Science diplomacy will continue to play a vital role in addressing global climate challenges and promoting mutual understanding among nations.
- High profile science diplomacy successes in institution-building, include the Centre for Nuclear Research (CERN) located near Geneva in Switzerland and counting 23 European nations as its member states.
- In turn, CERN helped establish the Synchrotron-light for Experimental Science and Applications in the Middle East, known under the acronym SESAME, representing a top research center for physics in the Middle East. SESAME is based in

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Jordan and has eight member states from the Middle East, and officially opened in 2017. Science and Applications in the Middle East (SESAME), a research facility based in Jordan. Its members are Bahrain, Cyprus, Egypt, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Pakistan, Palestine, and Turkey. This is notable as the diplomatic relationships between some members are very strained. Iran and Israel, for example, have not had direct diplomatic relationships since 1979.

- Scientists in the UK worked with scientists from the Democratic People's Republic of Korea to study Mt. Paektu. The collaboration resulted in a successful imaging of the crust beneath the iconic volcano.
- A collaboration between two TWAS Fellows—led to an opportunity to distribute a new, inexpensive, India-produced hepatitis B vaccine to people in Pakistan. The initiative was called Vaccines for Peace.
- Rwanda, Uganda, and, DR Congo share the territory of Virunga National Park, a UNESCO world heritage site famous for its rich biodiversity including endangered mountain gorillas. Such cooperation requires interaction with scientific advisors but also goodwill and expertise in diluting potential conflicts.
- The Newton Fund for Science and Innovation for Development and Diplomacy, a program between the UK and 16 partner countries to strengthen science and innovation capacity by investing in individual researchers and scientific collaborations.

In the realm of climate change and health, science diplomacy is particularly crucial for addressing the intricate relationships between environmental factors, human health, and sustainable development. By facilitating international collaboration and knowledge sharing, science diplomacy can help nations develop effective strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change, improve public health outcomes, and promote sustainable development. Through science diplomacy, nations can work together to address the complex global challenges of the 21st century, driving progress toward a more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable future.

Science diplomacy is particularly vital for the OIC Member states, which face unique development challenges that require access to scientific progress to address. The global South encompasses countries with diverse economic, social, and environmental contexts, each with distinct needs and priorities. To meet these varied development needs, science diplomacy plays a crucial role in facilitating access to scientific knowledge, technology, and innovation. Many of these needs are encapsulated in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to eradicate poverty, promote sustainable development, and ensure a healthy and prosperous life for all. Examples of the development needs in the OIC Member States that can be addressed through science diplomacy include:

- Improving agricultural productivity and food security in Africa through access to climate-resilient crop varieties and sustainable farming practices

- Enhancing public health outcomes in OIC Member States through collaboration on infectious disease research and vaccine development
- Supporting sustainable energy transitions in Latin America through knowledge sharing on renewable energy technologies and grid management
- Addressing water scarcity and quality issues in the Middle East and North Africa through scientific cooperation on water conservation and treatment technologies

By leveraging science diplomacy, countries in the global South can tap into the global scientific community's expertise, resources, and innovation, enabling them to leapfrog traditional development pathways and achieve their sustainable development goals more effectively.

There are some very important challenges that need international cooperation and collaboration in which Science Diplomacy can play an effective role, just to mention a few that need immediate attention.

1. Climate Change

Science Diplomacy can help in Collaborating on climate research, mitigation, and adaptation strategies, in sharing knowledge on climate modeling, scenario planning, and impact assessment.

2. Health

In the health sector science Diplomacy can play an effective role by Sharing knowledge on pandemic preparedness, global health security, and health innovation, Collaboration on infectious disease research, vaccine development, and healthcare systems strengthening

3. Sustainable Development

Science Diplomacy is very effective in addressing SDG-related challenges through joint research and policy initiatives. Focusing on sustainable energy, water management, and food security

4. Scientific Innovation

Scientific innovation is a critical area where global collaboration is essential to address the complex challenges of the 21st century. Fostering collaboration on emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), biotechnology, and clean energy can drive breakthroughs and accelerate progress towards sustainable development. Sharing knowledge on innovation ecosystems, entrepreneurship, and technology transfer can help nations build capacity, enhance competitiveness, and create jobs. However, these challenges cannot be addressed in isolation; they require a global response from both the scientific and policy-making communities.

The complexities of climate change, health pandemics, sustainable development, and scientific innovations are too vast for any single nation to tackle alone with its own resources. The interconnectedness of these challenges demands a global diplomacy

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approach, where nations work together to share knowledge, resources, and expertise. By doing so, we can:

- Develop and deploy AI solutions to tackle climate change, improve healthcare outcomes, and optimize resource allocation
- Leverage biotechnology to address global health challenges, develop sustainable agriculture practices, and create innovative materials
- Accelerate the transition to clean energy and reduce greenhouse gas emissions through collaborative research and development.
- Build resilient and sustainable innovation ecosystems that foster entrepreneurship, job creation, and economic growth

Through global diplomacy, nations can pool their strengths, address common challenges, and create a more equitable and prosperous future. By working together, we can harness the power of scientific innovation to drive progress toward the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and create a better world for future generations.

1. Joint Research Projects

- Collaborative proposals for funding and implementation should involve multiple stakeholders and integrate diverse perspectives.
- Focus on interdisciplinary research that addresses complex global challenges, drives innovation, and has potential for significant impact.
- Ensure that proposals align with priority areas and incorporate capacity-building components for all parties involved.
- Develop clear guidelines for proposal development, submission, and review to ensure transparency and accountability

2. Scientific Workshops and Conferences

- Regular meetings to share knowledge, expertise, and best practices
- Facilitate networking, collaboration, and partnership building

3. Policy Dialogues

- High-level discussions to inform policy-making with scientific evidence
- Ensure data-driven decision-making, policy coherence, and alignment with global agendas

4. Capacity Building Programs

- Training and education initiatives for researchers, policymakers, and diplomats
- Focus on science communication, policy engagement, and diplomacy skills

Pakistan Science Diplomacy Initiative (SDI)

In 2016, the “Science Diplomacy Initiative” (SDI), launched by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Pakistan, represents a pioneering effort to embed science and technology within the diplomatic framework of the country. This initiative, developed under the Science Diplomacy Division, aims to enhance Pakistan’s global scientific footprint by promoting cooperation with international stakeholders, including research institutes, multinational corporations, international organizations, and universities. The SDI is a testament to Pakistan’s recognition of the vital role that science and technology play in addressing global challenges and fostering international collaboration. Objectives of the Science Diplomacy Initiative The SDI was established with several key objectives:

1. **Strengthening International Scientific Cooperation:** One of the primary goals of the SDI is to build and strengthen relationships with global scientific communities. By facilitating partnerships with international research institutes and universities, Pakistan aims to collaborate on cutting-edge research and innovation.
2. **Enhancing Science and Technology Capacity:** The initiative seeks to elevate Pakistan’s capacity in science and technology by enabling knowledge transfer and access to advanced technologies through international collaborations
3. **Promoting Sustainable Development:** SDI aligns with global sustainable development goals (SDGs), particularly those related to health, climate change, and education. By leveraging scientific knowledge and research, the initiative supports the development of solutions to pressing global challenges.
4. **Engaging in Multilateral Scientific Dialogues:** Through SDI, Pakistan actively participates in multilateral forums and dialogues that shape global science policies. This engagement helps to position Pakistan as a key player in international science diplomacy.
5. **Building Networks and Partnerships:** The initiative emphasizes the creation of networks between Pakistani scientists and their international counterparts. These networks are crucial for fostering long-term collaborations and ensuring the flow of knowledge and expertise.

The initiative of MoFA is now further strengthened and complemented by the Ministerial Committee of Science and Technology (COMSTECH) of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) As an organization advocating the centrality of science and technology for prosperity, human development, and social progress for over 29 years among its Member States. COMSTECH has long practiced the principles of Science Diplomacy in its conventional dimensions. This has helped raise awareness, facilitated scientific exchanges, and allowed international collaborative projects and research under its umbrella. The recent launch of the COMSTECH Science Communication and Diplomacy Program is a new approach toward addressing the needs of scientists, diplomats, journalists, and policy-makers to build peace among nations using scientific knowledge and principles to allow informed decision-making. OIC–COMSTECH

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under this program has now formed a Science Communication and Diplomacy Group in 2023, which has taken this science communication program seriously as it provides many solutions to international problems.

The first step of this program towards enhancing science communication in Pakistan was to identify and empower scientific communicators and diplomats. To achieve this, a 3-Day International Conference on Science Communication and Diplomacy was organized in February 2023. Renowned scholars and experts gathered to share their insights and recommendations on effective science communication strategies.

Building on the conference's success, the Science Communication Advisory Committee (SCAC) was formed under the umbrella of COMSTECH (scac.comstech.org). The committee comprises 8 permanent members and 14 temporary members from various cities across Pakistan, ensuring diverse perspectives and expertise. To formalize training programs, SCAC developed comprehensive manuals for 3-day, 5-day, 2-credit hour, and 3-credit hour courses, floated to serve as a foundation for capacity-building initiatives in science communication and diplomacy.

In addition to the academic courses, SCAC has conducted numerous training courses, including "Science Communication and Diplomacy in Agriculture in different universities. These courses aim to equip participants with the skills to effectively communicate scientific information to diverse audiences.

To further disseminate knowledge and best practices of science communication, a joint initiative between SDI-MoFA, and SCAC-OIC-COMSTECH, led to the launch of the Journal of Science Communication and Diplomacy. This publication provides a platform for scholars and practitioners to share their research, experiences, and insights on science communication and diplomacy. Besides this, the Science Communication and Diplomacy form launched an extensive program to publish Monographs on the role of Science Communication in different fields. Two of them have already been published, covering science communication in agriculture, and climate change.

Recommendations:

1. Establish a Science Diplomacy Network:
 - Connect researchers, policymakers, diplomats, and industry representatives.
 - Facilitate communication, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing
2. Identify Priority Areas:
 - Determine key areas for collaboration based on national interests and global challenges
 - Ensure alignment with international agendas, such as the SDGs and Paris Agreement
3. Develop Joint Research Proposals:
 - Collaborative proposals for funding and implementation
 - Focus on interdisciplinary research, innovation, and impact
4. Monitor Progress and Evaluate Impact:
 - Regular assessment and evaluation of collaboration outcomes
 - Ensure accountability, transparency, and continuous improvement.

Conclusion

In conclusion, science diplomacy is a crucial instrument for fostering global cooperation in groundbreaking scientific research, cutting-edge technologies, and tackling pressing health challenges. By leveraging science diplomacy, Pakistan can unlock innovation, drive progress, and cultivate mutual understanding with international partners. To fully harness the potential of science diplomacy, it is essential to acknowledge and address the existing challenges and limitations. By doing so, we can amplify the impact of science diplomacy, promote the peaceful resolution of conflicts, and create a more equitable, prosperous, and sustainable future for all nations. Through collective efforts and collaborative spirit, science diplomacy can become a powerful tool for addressing the complex global challenges of the 21st century. We can harness its full potential to create a better future for all.”

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The Need for Science Communication for Techno-Nationalist Development in Pakistan

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Abstract

Science communication is an essential component for the socio-economic advancement of any nation, especially for countries like Pakistan, which aims to achieve technological self-reliance and innovation – techno-nationalism. This paper describes the crucial function of science communication in cultivating public understanding, bolstering policy-making, catalyzing innovation, shaping national identity, augmenting education, and mitigating misinformation. Through targeted initiatives, science communication can enhance societal engagement with scientific endeavors, promote evidence-based policymaking, and foster an environment conducive to scientific and technological progress, ultimately contributing to the nation's growth and self-sufficiency. By analyzing the current paradigm and suggesting strategic interventions, this study underscores the potential of proficient science communication as a driver for techno-nationalist development in Pakistan. In addition, this paper explores future prospects, emphasizing the need for continuous improvement in science communication to adapt to emerging technologies and global scientific trends, ensuring sustained innovation and techno-nationalist development.

Keywords: Science Communication, Socio-Economic Advancement, Techno-Nationalist Development, Scientific & Technological Progress, National Development, Techno-nationalism.

Key Insights:

- Science communication is instrumental in shaping national identity and enhances science literacy.
- It supports public understanding, evidence-based policymaking, and drive innovation.
- Strategic initiatives can increase societal engagement with science and reduce misinformation.
- Continuous improvement in science communication is vital for adapting the global scientific trends and sustaining national development.
- It is essential for Pakistan's socio-economic advancement and technological self-reliance.

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1. Introduction

Science and technology are integral to the advancement of contemporary nations, serving as catalysts for economic growth, societal well-being, and global competitiveness. In the context of Pakistan, a nation characterized by a rapidly expanding population and multifaceted socio-economic challenges, the strategic deployment of science and technology is essential for attaining sustainable development and enhancing its position in the global arena. Techno-nationalist development underscores the importance of achieving self-reliance in technological innovation (Gopikrishna et al., 2024). This paradigm integrates national identity with scientific and technological progress, promoting a vision where technological advancements are not merely adopted but indigenously developed to reinforce national technological sovereignty and economic resilience (Dewan, 2022; Gopikrishna et al., 2024). The pursuit of techno-nationalist development necessitates a comprehensive and cohesive approach to science communication.

Effective science communication is a cornerstone in actualizing techno-nationalist vision. It plays a critical role in engaging the public with scientific and technological discourses, thereby fostering a culture of curiosity and appreciation for scientific endeavors. Through clear and accessible communication, complex scientific concepts can be demystified, enhancing public understanding and participation. Science communication is instrumental in informing and shaping policy. Policymakers, equipped with accurate and timely scientific information, are better positioned to formulate and implement policies that support innovation and address socio-economic challenges (Johnson; Szüdi et al., 2022). This evidence-based approach to policy-making ensures that technological advancements are aligned with national development goals and public interests.

Open innovation and open science are additional domains significantly influenced by effective science communication. By highlighting breakthroughs and fostering dialogue between scientists, industry stakeholders, and the public, science communication can stimulate creative solutions to pressing issues, drive economic growth, and establish a robust innovation ecosystem (Sanabria-Z, Cruz-Sandoval, Moreno-Romo, Bosch-Gómez, & Ramírez-Montoya, 2024). In addition, a scientifically literate society, cultivated through sustained science communication efforts, is crucial for the long-term success of techno-nationalist development. Such a society values and understands the impact of science and technology, supports research and development initiatives, and actively contributes to the nation's scientific and technological endeavors.

Utilizing science communication to engage the public, inform policy, stimulate innovation, and promote scientific literacy is crucial for Pakistan to achieve sustainable techno-nationalist development and secure its future as a competitive global player. Effective science communication enhances public understanding and participation, supports the creation of evidence-based policies, drives technological innovation, and cultivates a scientifically literate society (Rautela, 2024). By strategically focusing on these areas, Pakistan can harness its scientific and technological potential, ensur-

ing alignment with national development goals and global competitiveness. This approach will enable Pakistan to address socio-economic challenges, foster continuous innovation, and solidify its position in the global technological landscape.

2. Public Understanding and Engagement

2.1. Awareness and Literacy

Science communication elevates public awareness and comprehension of scientific principles and innovations, which is essential for cultivating a society that values and engages with science. This engagement is fundamental for fostering informed decision-making and facilitating collective progress (Reddy, Parker, & Hannan, 2020). Implementing initiatives such as science fairs, public lectures, and targeted media campaigns can markedly enhance scientific literacy within the general populace. These efforts contribute to building a knowledgeable society capable of critically evaluating scientific information and actively participating in scientific discourse. Consequently, a well-informed public is better equipped to support and contribute to scientific endeavors, driving societal advancement and innovation.

In Pakistan background, one notable initiative is the collaboration between the government, the World Health Organization (WHO), and local community leaders to disseminate accurate information about the polio vaccine. Through a series of public awareness campaigns, including televised public service announcements, radio programs, and community meetings, these efforts effectively communicated the scientific facts about the vaccine's safety and efficacy. Religious and community leaders were also engaged to endorse the vaccination program, which helped build trust among skeptical communities.

2.2. Informed Decision-Making

A scientifically informed populace is better positioned to make judicious decisions concerning technology, health, and environmental issues. Enhanced comprehension of scientific advancements enables citizens to actively engage in discourse and decision-making processes that influence their communities and the nation (Ryan et al., 2023). For instance, targeted awareness campaigns regarding renewable energy can elevate public support for sustainable energy policies and practices. This informed engagement fosters a proactive society that can critically assess and endorse innovations, thereby contributing to the formulation and implementation of policies that promote long-term sustainability and technological progress.

3. Policy Support

3.1. Evidence-Based Policies

Clear and effective science communication ensures policymakers have access to reliable, pertinent scientific data. This access facilitates the development and adoption of evidence-based policies that promote technological progress and address socio-economic challenges (Bag, 2023). For instance, effectively communicating re-

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search findings on climate change can catalyze the formulation and implementation of robust environmental policies. Such policies are grounded in scientific evidence, thus enhancing their efficacy and societal impact. Consequently, well-informed decision-making processes are established, enabling the creation of strategies that effectively integrate scientific advancements into national development plans, ultimately fostering sustainable growth and resilience.

A pertinent example of how effective science communication has influenced policy in Pakistan is the case of the polio eradication campaign. Pakistan, being one of the few countries where polio remains endemic, faced significant challenges in convincing the public about the safety and necessity of polio vaccinations due to widespread misinformation and mistrust. However, targeted science communication efforts played a crucial role in addressing these challenges and influencing health policy.

3.2. Public Support for Science Funding

Emphasizing the benefits of scientific research via media and public engagement is pivotal for garnering support for enhanced funding in science and technology sectors. Public endorsement is critical for sustained investment in research and development, which is indispensable for technological innovation and national advancement (Dwivedi et al., 2024). By showcasing the tangible impacts and potential of scientific endeavors, these communication efforts can mobilize public opinion and influence policymakers to allocate greater resources towards scientific research. This, in turn, facilitates a continuous cycle of innovation, driving economic growth and reinforcing the nation's competitive edge in the global technological landscape.

4. Innovation and Economic Growth

4.1. Stimulating Innovation

Science communication plays a critical role in stimulating innovation by effectively disseminating information about scientific achievements and technological advancements. This dissemination can catalyze the generation of novel ideas, entrepreneurial initiatives, and collaborative efforts between academic institutions and industry sectors. By prominently showcasing successful innovations, science communication can inspire and motivate emerging entrepreneurs and researchers to develop technological solutions addressing national challenges (Baram-Tsabari et al., 2020). Such exposure not only fosters a culture of creativity and enterprise but also contributes to economic growth by encouraging the translation of scientific discoveries into practical applications. Consequently, a well-structured science communication strategy can drive progress and reinforce a nation's capacity for innovation.

4.2. Attracting Talent

Effective science communication is instrumental in attracting both domestic and international talent to Pakistan's science and technology sectors. By prominently showcasing the country's advancements and opportunities, such communication strategies can appeal to skilled professionals and researchers, encouraging their participation in

the local scientific community. This influx of talent contributes to the creation of a dynamic and innovative environment, essential for fostering research and technological development. Highlighting the nation's progress and opportunities not only enhances its global reputation but also facilitates the establishment of collaborative networks that drive further innovation and development. Thus, a strategic focus on science communication can significantly bolster the country's capacity to attract and retain top-tier talent, ultimately advancing its scientific and technological capabilities.

5. National Identity and Pride

5.1. Showcasing Achievements

Science communication plays a crucial role in fostering national pride by highlighting a country's scientific achievements and technological advancements. By effectively communicating these successes, science communication helps build a sense of pride and identity among citizens, showcasing the nation's capabilities and progress on both a national and global stage. This promotion not only enhances the national image but also galvanizes collective efforts towards further scientific and technological advancement (Gordon & Mihailidis, 2022). Celebrating significant milestones, such as space missions or breakthroughs in medical research, can unify the nation under a shared objective of progress. These celebratory events underscore the country's capabilities and potential, inspiring both current and future generations to contribute to the scientific enterprise. By creating a narrative of national achievement and progress, science communication can foster a cohesive and forward-looking society dedicated to continuous innovation and development. For instance, when Pakistan successfully launched the Badar-1 satellite, strategic science communication highlighted this achievement as a significant milestone, fostering a sense of national pride and unity. Celebrating such scientific accomplishments not only elevates national morale but also reinforces the public's belief in their country's potential to achieve technological and scientific breakthroughs.

5.2. Techno-Nationalism

Science communication serves as a strategic instrument for advancing techno-nationalist development by underscoring the critical importance of self-reliance in technology. It emphasizes that scientific and technological progress is not merely a facet of modernity but a cornerstone of national development and sovereignty. Through targeted communication strategies, the narrative of self-sufficiency in technology can be effectively conveyed, highlighting how indigenous innovations contribute to economic resilience and geopolitical stability. By showcasing the interdependence between scientific advancements and national development, science communication can inspire collective efforts toward achieving technological independence. This involves illustrating successful examples of homegrown technologies and innovations that address local challenges, thereby reinforcing the capability and potential within the nation. In addition, effective science communication can galvanize public and private sector support for research and development, fostering an environment where sci-

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entific inquiry and technological innovation are prioritized and valued (Montemayor, Navarro, & Navarro). It can also facilitate the creation of policies that support domestic technological initiatives, ensuring that the country's technological infrastructure is robust and sustainable. In essence, science communication can mobilize a unified national agenda focused on technological self-reliance, driving forward the vision of techno-nationalist development and positioning the country as a leader in the global technological landscape.

6. Education and Workforce Development

6.1. STEM Education

Promoting STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education through science communication initiatives is crucial for developing a skilled workforce equipped to address future technological challenges. Implementing educational programs, workshops, summer camps, and interactive science center effectively engages students, fostering interest and encouraging pursuit of careers in STEM fields (Bicer & Lee, 2023). These initiatives not only enhance scientific literacy but also provide practical experience and inspiration, essential for cultivating a new generation of innovators and problem-solvers. By strategically promoting STEM education, a nation can ensure a continuous supply of qualified professionals capable of driving technological advancement and sustaining economic growth.

STEM education initiatives are fundamental to the broader goals of techno-nationalist development, particularly in a country like Pakistan that is striving for technological self-reliance and innovation. By fostering a robust STEM education system, Pakistan can cultivate a highly skilled workforce that is capable of driving technological advancements and innovation. This skilled workforce is crucial for reducing dependence on foreign technologies and expertise, thus enhancing national self-reliance.

Investing in STEM education equips students with the knowledge and skills needed to contribute to critical sectors such as information technology, engineering, biotechnology, and renewable energy. These sectors are pivotal for Pakistan's economic growth and for addressing pressing socio-economic challenges. By aligning STEM education initiatives with national development priorities, Pakistan can create a pipeline of talent that is not only adept at solving complex problems but also capable of developing indigenous technologies that bolster the country's technological sovereignty.

6.2. Bridging Gaps

Science communication plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between academia, industry, and the public. By aligning educational curricula with industry demands and technological advancements, it ensures the development of a workforce possessing pertinent skills and knowledge. This alignment facilitates the creation of collaborative platforms and industry partnerships, enhancing the practical application of academic research. Through effective communication, academia can better understand industry needs, leading to curricula that prepare students for real-world challenges

(Baram-Tsabari et al., 2020). In addition, public engagement initiatives can demystify scientific concepts, fostering a society that values and supports scientific endeavors. Thus, science communication not only promotes educational and industrial synergy but also contributes to a well-informed and skilled populace, driving national progress and innovation.

In Pakistan, STEM education initiatives that are integrated into national development strategies can foster a culture of innovation, entrepreneurship and bridge the gap between academia and industry. For example, by providing opportunities for hands-on learning and encouraging collaboration between academia and industry, Pakistan can stimulate the development of new technologies and startups that contribute to the country's technological ecosystem. This approach not only strengthens the domestic economy but also positions Pakistan as a competitive player in the global technological landscape.

7. Addressing Misinformation

7.1. Countering Misinformation

In an era where misinformation proliferates swiftly, effective science communication is critical for countering pseudoscience and false information. Clear, accurate, and accessible dissemination of scientific knowledge enables the public to distinguish credible information, a necessity for technological advancement. By ensuring that scientific information is presented in an understandable and reliable manner, science communication fortifies public trust in scientific institutions and methodologies. This trust is essential for fostering informed decision-making and encouraging public support for scientific and technological initiatives (Weiss, 2024). Consequently, robust science communication serves as a bulwark against misinformation, safeguarding the integrity of scientific discourse and promoting continuous technological progress.

In Pakistan, misinformation poses significant challenges, particularly in areas such as public health and technological adoption. For example, false claims about vaccine safety, especially during polio vaccination campaigns, have led to vaccine hesitancy and resistance, undermining public health efforts. To combat such misinformation, public awareness campaigns that provide clear, evidence-based information in local languages can help dispel myths and alleviate fears. Engaging trusted community and religious leaders to endorse scientific truths can also build public trust and counter misinformation.

7.2. Building Trust

Transparent and accurate communication fosters public trust in scientific institutions and the advantages of technological advancements. This trust is fundamental for securing public acceptance and support for scientific and technological progress. By engaging the public in meaningful dialogue and addressing their concerns, science communication can reinforce this trust and cultivate a culture of scientific inquiry (Montemayor et al.). Open channels of communication enable the public to better

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understand the processes and benefits of scientific endeavors, leading to informed support for innovation and research. Consequently, robust science communication is vital for establishing a well-informed society that values and actively participates in scientific and technological development.

In Pakistan context, strengthening science and digital literacy through educational programs can empower the public to critically evaluate information online, while leveraging social media platforms to disseminate accurate scientific information can help counteract false narratives. Providing training for scientists, educators, and journalists on effective science communication can enhance their ability to convey complex information clearly and address misinformation directly. These steps can help foster a scientifically literate society and support Pakistan's broader goals of techno-nationalist development and public trust in science and technology.

8. Strategies for Enhancing Science Communication in Pakistan

8.1. Media Collaboration

Collaborating with media outlets to distribute scientific information via television, radio, and digital platforms can effectively reach a wide audience. Science programs, documentaries, and news segments focused on scientific advancements are instrumental in raising public awareness and interest in science and technology (Gordon & Mihailidis, 2022). These media initiatives can demystify complex scientific concepts, making them accessible to the general populace. By leveraging the broad reach of various media channels, science communication can enhance scientific literacy, promote public engagement, and inspire future generations to pursue careers in STEM fields (Chen, Hardjo, Sonnert, Hui, & Sadler, 2023). This strategic partnership between science communicators and media entities is essential for fostering an informed and technologically progressive society.

To effectively implement science communication strategies in Pakistan, it is essential to tailor these efforts to align with the country's cultural values and socio-political environment. One practical approach is to leverage the widespread influence of local media, including television, radio, and digital platforms, to disseminate scientific information in local languages. By producing science programs, documentaries, and news segments that are culturally relevant and easily accessible, science communication can reach a broader audience and resonate more deeply with the public.

8.2. Public Engagement Events

Organizing science fairs, exhibitions, and public lectures effectively engages the community and highlights scientific advancements. These events offer interactive and hands-on experiences, rendering science accessible and stimulating for individuals across all age groups. By facilitating direct interaction with scientific concepts and innovations, such initiatives promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of science. They serve as dynamic platforms for demonstrating the practical applications of scientific research, thereby inspiring curiosity and enthusiasm among participants. Through these experiential learning opportunities, science communication fosters a

culture of inquiry and supports the development of a scientifically literate society (Dwivedi et al., 2024; Gordon & Mihailidis, 2022).

Given Pakistan's diverse socio-political landscape, it is also crucial to work closely with community leaders and influencers who can advocate for science and technology within their communities. Engaging religious leaders, who hold significant sway in many parts of Pakistan, to support science communication initiatives can help bridge the gap between science and cultural beliefs, fostering a more inclusive approach to scientific education and outreach.

8.3. Educational Programs

Implementing science communication training programs for scientists and educators can significantly enhance their proficiency in conveying complex information to non-specialist audiences. Workshops, summer camps and courses focused on effective communication strategies can amplify the effectiveness of their outreach initiatives (Bicer & Lee, 2023; Daniel, Ament, McConnell, Marty, & Idema, 2023). These programs equip scientists and educators with the skills to translate technical jargon into accessible language, thereby broadening the reach and impact of scientific information. Enhanced communication capabilities facilitate greater public engagement and understanding, fostering a more scientifically informed society. By investing in such training, the scientific community can improve its outreach efforts, ensuring that advancements in science and technology are effectively communicated and appreciated by the broader public.

Another strategy involves collaborating with educational institutions to integrate science communication into the curriculum at various educational levels. Incorporating local examples of scientific achievements and addressing everyday scientific issues relevant to the Pakistani context can make science education more relatable and engaging for students. In addition, organizing community-based science fairs, exhibitions, and public lectures in collaboration with local schools and universities can foster grassroots engagement and encourage public participation in scientific discourse.

8.4. Government Initiatives

Promoting governmental support for science communication through funding, policy initiatives, and public outreach programs is essential. Government-sponsored campaigns and incentives can cultivate a culture of science communication and ensure its integration into national development strategies. These efforts can enhance the visibility and impact of scientific endeavors, facilitating informed public discourse and policy-making (Nix & Houfek, 2023). By prioritizing science communication in national agendas, the government can foster a scientifically literate society, driving innovation and technological advancement. This strategic support is crucial for aligning scientific progress with socio-economic goals, ultimately contributing to the nation's growth and global competitiveness.

Policy-level support is essential for the successful implementation of these strategies. The government can play a pivotal role by providing funding and creating policies

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that encourage public and private sector investment in science communication. Establishing partnerships between government bodies, educational institutions, and media organizations can facilitate coordinated efforts to enhance science literacy and public trust in science and technology. By considering Pakistan's unique cultural and socio-political context, these strategies can be effectively implemented to foster a more scientifically literate society, promote national pride in scientific achievements, and support the country's long-term development goals.

9. Conclusion and Future Prospects

In Pakistan, enhancing science communication is crucial for fully leveraging its scientific and technological potential as effective science communication fosters public understanding, supports evidence-based policymaking, stimulates innovation, shape national identity, enhances education, and combats misinformation. By implementing strategic initiatives and nurturing a culture of proficient science communication, Pakistan can advance its techno-nationalist development objectives and establish itself as a leader in the global technological arena. These efforts will enable Pakistan to harness scientific advancements for socio-economic growth, ensuring that its technological progress aligns with national development goals and global competitiveness. Looking ahead, the continuous improvement of science communication will be essential for adapting to emerging technologies and global scientific trends. Future prospects include the integration of advanced digital platforms and AI-driven tools to enhance the accessibility and impact of science communication. Accentuating interdisciplinary collaboration between scientists, educators, and media professionals can further strengthen public engagement and scientific literacy. In addition, fostering international partnerships in science communication will allow Pakistan to stay abreast of global trends and innovations, ensuring that the nation remains competitive on the world stage. Continuous investment in science communication training and infrastructure will be energetic for addressing future challenges, promoting sustained innovation, and driving national development in an increasingly technology-driven world. As Pakistan strengthens its science communication infrastructure, it will be better positioned to address future challenges and opportunities, driving sustained innovation and techno-nationalist development.

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Promoting Science Literacy Through Media Education

Promoting Science Literacy Through Media Education: Insight From Media Students In Rawalpindi And Islamabad, Pakistan

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Abstract

Understanding science is crucial, for making informed decisions and improving comprehension of complex scientific topics. In Pakistan, where addressing development issues requires the public to engage with science the role of media professionals in communicating information is vital. This research explores how science communication education is being taught in media departments at universities in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The focus is on students' awareness, perceptions, challenges, and suggestions for improvement. Through qualitative methods, 75 media students (40 males and 35 females) participated in structured interviews to share their insights and views. The results show that there's a lack of awareness among students about science communication with not realizing its importance or having access to necessary resources. Barriers include integration into the curriculum, faculty knowledge in this area and a lack of collaboration across disciplines. Despite these obstacles students acknowledged the significance of science in their lives. Suggested ways to enhance science communication, such as adding courses to the curriculum hosting workshops and fostering partnerships between science and media departments. This study underscores the need for educational changes to boost literacy among media students so they can effectively communicate science information and contribute positively to public understanding of science, in Pakistan. The knowledge acquired from this study forms the basis, for creating custom initiatives that tackle the obstacles and utilize students' suggestions to enhance science communication, in media education.

Keywords: Science literacy, students, media education, Curriculum development, Interdisciplinary collaboration, Pakistan

1. Introduction

Effective communication, in the field of science is crucial for connecting communities with the public promoting better comprehension and involvement in scientific matters. In today's world driven by advancements in science and technology the ability to communicate science effectively is vital for making informed decisions and advancing society. This holds importance in countries like Pakistan, where a solid grasp of science is key to national progress and addressing socio-economic issues.

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Despite its importance, science communication faces challenges in Pakistan, such as educational resources, insufficient integration into the educational system and cultural perspectives on science. These obstacles impede the spread of knowledge and the development of a educated population. University students are the future leaders and professionals and their grasp of science communication can shape public perceptions and enhance outreach efforts, most importantly students studying media, are crucial to overcoming these challenges. This study aims to evaluate the knowledge and understanding of science communication among media students in Pakistani universities, while also exploring their perspectives on how to improve science communication initiatives.

The research focuses on identifying gaps in awareness, highlighting challenges, and collecting recommendations for enhancing science literacy and public engagement with science in Pakistan. By examining students' knowledge, opinions, and suggestions, this study seeks to provide actionable insights that can strengthen science communication efforts in the country.

The study goals include:

1. To assess the existing level of awareness and comprehension of science communication among media students at universities.
2. To investigate media student's perspectives on the significance and current status of science communication within their institutions.
3. To identify obstacles to science communication as perceived by the students.
4. To collect recommendations from students, on how to enhance science communication initiatives in Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

Communicating science is vital, for connecting scientists with the public. Effective science communication helps people grasp ideas impacts policymaking and promotes informed choices (Bubela et al., 2009). In media education, understanding science is crucial, for preparing journalists and media experts to communicate intricate scientific details to various groups (Schäfer, 2012).

2.1. Global Perspectives on Science Communication Education

Science communication plays a vital role in bridging the gap between scientists and the public. Effective science communication not only helps individuals understand complex scientific ideas but also influences policymaking and promotes informed decision-making (Bubela et al., 2009). Globally, there is an increasing recognition of the need to integrate science communication into media education. In developed nations like the United States and the United Kingdom, science communication training is widely recognized as essential for media professionals to effectively convey intricate scientific details to a diverse audience (Dunwoody, 2008; Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009).

Studies from these countries highlight how science communication courses enhance

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critical thinking, improve data analysis skills, and foster better collaboration between media professionals and scientists (Schäfer, 2012). For example, research in the US and UK has shown that media students trained in science communication are better equipped to present accurate and clear information to the public, preventing misinformation (Weitkamp & Eidsvaag, 2014). Pakistan should have similar training programs that cater to the local media landscape, help to fill the existing educational gaps.

2.2. The Role of Media in Science Literacy

Media professionals serve as a crucial link between scientists and the general public, and play important role in promoting science literacy paramount. According to Akinwale and Ojebode (2018), media students must learn how to communicate scientific concepts effectively to ensure the public receives accurate and reliable information. In under-developed countries like Pakistan where science literacy is low, media professionals' ability to communicate scientific ideas is even more important.

However, without proper education in science communication, media professionals may misrepresent and oversimplify complex scientific issues, potentially leading to public misunderstandings or even mistrust in science (Allchin, 2022). This has been a growing concern globally, as misinformation can spread easily through media channels. The role of media in shaping public understanding of science emphasizes the need to include science communication in media curricula, ensuring that future journalists are prepared to report on scientific matters accurately.

2.3. Challenges in Science Communication in Pakistan

Despite its growing global importance, science communication in Pakistan remains an underdeveloped field, especially within media education programs. There is little to no integration of science communication in university media curricula, which hinders the development of qualified science communicators (Mahmood, 2018). This gap is attributed to a lack of awareness among educators and limited resources available for science communication courses (Mustafa et al., 2022).

The shortage of skilled faculty members who can teach science communication further exacerbates the issue. Faculty members often lack the necessary expertise or access to training materials, making it difficult to introduce and sustain science communication education in universities. This absence of foundational training not only affects the ability of media students to understand and report on science but also limits their potential as effective communicators capable of addressing national socio-economic challenges through science literacy (Lee & Luykx, 2013).

2.4. The Need for Curriculum Integration

There is a pressing need to integrate science communication into media education curricula in Pakistan. Universities must prioritize creating courses that enable media students to communicate scientific ideas clearly and accurately. Promoting collaboration between science and media departments could facilitate the development of tailored educational programs (Ali & Fahad, 2020). Such collaboration would foster

interdisciplinary learning, allowing media students to engage more deeply with scientific concepts and bridge the gap between scientists and the public.

Moreover, the inclusion of science communication training in the curriculum would empower media professionals to take on more active roles in enhancing public understanding of science, particularly in Pakistan, where science literacy remains low. Tailoring these programs to the unique challenges of Pakistan's media landscape could result in more effective public engagement with scientific issues, fostering a more informed and science-literate society.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research adopts a qualitative method to investigate the status of science communication education, among media students at universities in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Semi-structured interviews were carried out to gain insights into students' views, obstacles and recommendations regarding science communication. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling to ensure a representation of students from different media departments. This method was selected to capture perspectives on science communication education. The interviews featured ended inquiries covering; Awareness and Understanding; Students' familiarity with and perception of the significance of science communication. Challenges; Difficulties encountered in accessing science communication resources and education. Suggestions; Proposals for integrating and enhancing science communication in their curriculum. The interviews were conducted either face to face or through platforms depending on availability. Each interview lasted around 30 – 45 minutes. All the interviews were recorded with the participants consent and data analysis and accuracy. Thematic analysis was employed to scrutinize and interpret patterns and themes within the interview responses.

4. Findings

4.1. Knowledge and Awareness of Science Communication

Only 10.67% of students were familiar with the term “science communication., highlighting a significant gap in their knowledge of this field.

One student shared, “I've heard about science communication, but we haven't had any discussions or courses on it in our department.” This lack of structured education reflects findings in other contexts, where science communication is often underrepresented in media curricula (Weitkamp & Eidsvaag, 2014; Schäfer, 2012).

4.2. Perceived Importance of Science in Everyday Life

Despite the limited understanding of science communication, a majority of students (64%) recognized the importance of science in their lives. This is consistent with broader trends showing that individuals increasingly value science's role in societal development and personal well-being (Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009; Dunwoody, 2008).

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A female student remarked, “Science impacts every aspect of our lives, from health to technology. It’s important that we learn how to communicate it.” This observation aligns with global research emphasizing the role of media professionals in disseminating scientific knowledge (Bubela et al., 2009; Schäfer, 2012).

4.3. Suggestions for Curriculum Integration

88% of students suggested that science communication should be integrated into their academic curriculum. This echo calls for integrating science communication training into journalism and media programs to equip future media professionals with the necessary skills (Dunwoody, 2008; Akinwale & Ojebode, 2018).

One student stated, “Including science communication as part of our regular coursework would help us understand how to present scientific topics to the public.” Previous research also supports the need for curriculum changes to ensure media students can effectively engage with science (Hardiansyah, 2022).

4.4. Recommendations for Workshops and Practical Training

88% of students recommended the introduction of workshops and seminars for hands-on learning in science communication. This suggestion is in line with studies advocating for practical training and interdisciplinary workshops to enhance science communication skills (Ali & Fahad, 2020; Weitkamp & Eidsvaag, 2014).

A student suggested, “Workshops and seminars would provide us with practical skills to communicate science effectively, not just theory.” The idea that hands-on learning significantly improves students’ ability to communicate scientific content (Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009).

These findings reveal a clear need for structured education in science communication, as well as practical training opportunities to equip students with the skills to communicate scientific knowledge effectively.

4.5. Challenges

80% of students cited the lack of curriculum integration as a major barrier. One student expressed frustration stating, “Our curriculum doesn’t even touch on science communication. How are we supposed to learn something that isn’t even included?” This sentiment was shared by others emphasizing the importance of education in science communication.

Additionally, resource limitations (74.67%) and limited faculty expertise (69.33%) were also significant challenges. As one student emphasized, “Access, to journals and mentors who can help us grasp and convey concepts is crucial.”

4.6. Suggestions for Improvement

The ideas of media students, on how to improve science communication education show an approach to tackling the challenges they encounter. The suggested improvement was integrating science communication into the curriculum with 88% of stu-

dents favoring this idea indicating a strong interest in receiving formal education in this field. A male student expressed, “Having courses on science communication will prepare us for future roles in journalism.”

Additionally organizing workshops and seminars (88% of students) was seen as valuable with an emphasis, on the importance of hands-on learning experiences. One student recommended, “Engaging in workshops and seminars led by experts can help us learn through real world examples and practice our science communication skills effectively.”

The suggestion to improve resource accessibility (78.67% of students) underscores the necessity for universities to offer literature and resources essential for science communication. Lastly, the recommendation to collaborate with science departments (73.33% of students) highlights the advantages of learning. A student mentioned, “Collaborating with science departments can deepen our understanding of topics and enhance our communication abilities.”

5. Analysis

In order to tackle the issues and shortcomings, in educating people about science communication various approaches have been suggested;

5.1. Integrating Curriculum:

One proposed method involves including science communication classes within media programs to help students grasp concepts better and enhance their skills in conveying information effectively. These courses should focus on principles of science communication, media literacy, and critical thinking abilities needed for assessing arguments

5.2. Conducting Workshops and Seminars:

Another strategy is to organize workshops and seminars featuring experts in science communication. This hands-on approach can equip students with skills and real-world experience fostering interaction with professionals so that they can learn from concrete examples and apply science communication techniques

5.3. Enhancing Resource Accessibility

Improving the availability of literature and educational materials is essential for supporting students learning endeavors. Universities should invest in libraries subscriptions to journals and online resources to ensure students have the necessary information at their disposal.

5.4. Encouraging Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Encouraging collaboration, between departments specializing in science and media can offer students an education. Through courses and projects students can gain exposure to diverse perspectives that enhance their ability to communicate knowledge effectively to various audiences.

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6. Conclusion

The critical role of science communication in media education and highlights the challenges faced by universities in addressing this need. Key challenges such as lack of awareness, insufficient resources, and inadequate infrastructure hinder the development of proficient science communicators in Pakistan. However, these obstacles can be overcome through targeted interventions aimed at integrating science communication more thoroughly into university programs.

Universities should take several concrete steps to address these issues. First, they must introduce dedicated courses on science communication within media curricula to ensure that students are equipped with the essential skills needed to convey complex scientific information effectively. Additionally, conducting regular workshops and seminars will provide hands-on experience, allowing students to practice and refine their communication techniques. These workshops can be designed in collaboration with both media experts and scientists to offer real-world insights into the practice of science communication.

Universities must enhance access to resources by investing in educational materials and training platforms tailored to science communication. This also includes faculty development programs to ensure that educators are well-prepared to teach this subject. Collaboration between media and science departments should be encouraged to promote interdisciplinary learning opportunities, enabling students to engage with scientific research directly and develop a deeper understanding of how to communicate it effectively.

Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of these proposed changes, such as measuring the impact of science communication courses on students' abilities to convey scientific ideas. Additionally, studies should investigate the long-term outcomes of practical training sessions like workshops in improving public understanding of science. By adopting these strategies, universities can play a crucial role in advancing science literacy and empowering media professionals to make a significant impact on public comprehension of science.

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Leveraging Science Communication for Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Science and Technology Parks

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Abstract

Science and Technology Parks (STPs) serve as crucial ecosystems for fostering innovation and entrepreneurship by integrating academia, industry, and government efforts to drive technological advancements and economic growth. However, the success of STPs is heavily dependent on effective science communication, which extends beyond merely disseminating research findings. This research explores the pivotal role of science communication in enhancing the impact of STPs by facilitating knowledge transfer, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and raising public awareness. By effectively communicating scientific discoveries to industry professionals, policymakers, and the public, STPs can bridge the gap between research and its application, fostering the commercialization of innovations and contributing to broader societal and economic development. Case studies of renowned institutions such as Stanford Research Park and MIT demonstrate the significance of strategic science communication in transforming academic research into industrial innovation. Additionally, the study highlights the evolving landscape of science communication within OIC member countries, emphasizing the importance of tailored strategies to address regional challenges and opportunities. The paper concludes with recommendations for enhancing science communication practices within STPs, particularly in OIC member countries, through strategic investments, support from organizations like COMSTECH, and the development of a Science Communication Media Resource Kit. These initiatives are essential for maximizing the impact of STPs and driving sustainable innovation and entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Science Communication, Science and Technology Parks (STPs), Public Engagement, Digital Tools, Training Programs, Innovation Ecosystems, Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Introduction

Science and Technology Parks (STPs) have emerged as essential components of the global innovation landscape, functioning as dynamic ecosystems where academia, industry, and government intersect to drive technological advancements and economic

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growth. By providing a structured environment that supports research, development, and commercialization, STPs play a pivotal role in translating scientific discoveries into marketable products and services. These parks not only offer the physical infrastructure necessary for innovation but also foster a culture of entrepreneurship, where startups and established firms alike can thrive through access to cutting-edge research, state-of-the-art facilities, and a network of expertise.

Despite their potential, the success and impact of STPs are intricately tied to the effectiveness of science communication within these environments (Klemens Kappel 2019). Science communication, in this context, extends beyond the mere dissemination of research findings; it encompasses a wide array of activities aimed at ensuring that the knowledge generated within STPs is accessible, comprehensible, and actionable by diverse stakeholders, including researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and the broader public. Effective communication strategies are crucial for bridging the gap between scientific research and its application (Martinez, Brammer and Punyanunt-Carter 2023), facilitating the transfer of knowledge across disciplinary boundaries, and fostering the kind of interdisciplinary collaboration that is often necessary for innovation.

In the context of STPs, three foundational building blocks are crucial for maximizing their impact: the effective communication of research and innovations to industry, known as knowledge transfer; the breakdown of traditional academic and industrial silos to enable the convergence of diverse expertise and perspectives for solving complex challenges, referred to as interdisciplinary collaboration; and the strategic communication that raises support and interest from the general public and policymakers, termed public awareness (Martínez-Cañas, Ruiz-Palomino and Garcia-Haro 2021). Knowledge transfer ensures that the innovations developed within STPs are adopted by industry, facilitating commercialization and fostering economic growth. Interdisciplinary collaboration enables the fusion of diverse fields, essential for addressing complex scientific and technological challenges. Public awareness, meanwhile, plays a vital role in garnering support and creating a favorable environment for innovation. Together, these elements form a cohesive framework that supports the successful operation of STPs, driving innovation and entrepreneurship in a manner that contributes to broader societal and economic development.

Knowledge Transfer

Knowledge transfer is a crucial aspect of science communication that involves disseminating scientific findings to a broader audience. This process ensures that the benefits of research are not confined to academic circles but extend to industry professionals, policymakers, and the general public. Effective knowledge transfer can lead to several significant outcomes. By clearly communicating their findings, researchers can ensure that their discoveries are applied in real-world scenarios, leading to the development of new technologies, improved products, and innovative solutions to societal challenges. When scientific knowledge is effectively communicated to industry professionals, it can spur innovation and drive the development of new industries

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(Svend Tveden-Nyborg 2013); for example, breakthroughs in materials science can lead to the creation of new manufacturing processes, while advances in biotechnology can result in new medical treatments and pharmaceuticals.

Policymakers rely on accurate and timely scientific information to make informed decisions. By effectively communicating research findings, scientists can influence policy development, leading to regulations and initiatives that support scientific advancement and address critical issues such as climate change, public health, and technological innovation (Hassan 2019). Additionally, when the general public is informed about scientific discoveries, it can lead to increased interest and support for scientific research. This can manifest in various ways, including higher public funding for research institutions, greater participation in citizen science projects, and improved science literacy across the population.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Interdisciplinary collaboration is essential for addressing complex scientific and technological challenges that span multiple fields. Effective science communication plays a pivotal role in fostering such collaborations by breaking down silos, bridging the gaps between different disciplines, and allowing researchers to understand and appreciate the perspectives and methodologies of other fields (Fischhoff 2019). This can lead to the integration of diverse approaches and the development of comprehensive solutions to complex problems. Clear communication channels enable researchers from different disciplines to identify common interests and complementary skills, resulting in joint research projects that leverage the strengths of multiple fields and lead to groundbreaking discoveries and innovations.

Interdisciplinary collaboration often leads to the cross-pollination of ideas, where concepts and techniques from one field inspire novel applications in another; for example, principles from physics can be applied to biological systems, leading to advances in medical imaging and diagnostics. Additionally, effective communication fosters the development of robust research networks, where scientists from different disciplines can share resources, data, and expertise. These networks can accelerate the pace of discovery and enhance the overall impact of scientific research.

Public Awareness

Raising public awareness about research outcomes is essential for garnering support and interest in scientific endeavors. Effective communication to the public can result in increased public support; when the public is aware of the benefits and potential applications of scientific research, they are more likely to support funding initiatives and policies that promote scientific advancement (Motta 2018). This support can come in the form of votes for science-friendly candidates, advocacy for increased research funding, and participation in public consultations. Public awareness and support can lead to increased funding from both governmental and private sources. Philanthropic organizations and private investors are more likely to fund research initiatives that have demonstrated public interest and potential impact.

Policymakers are more likely to prioritize science and technology issues when there is strong public awareness and support. Effective communication can help the public understand the importance of scientific research in addressing societal challenges, leading to policies that foster innovation and support scientific institutions. Raising awareness about scientific research can improve overall science literacy, helping the public make informed decisions about their health, environment, and technology. This can lead to a more informed and engaged citizenry that values and supports scientific inquiry. Public awareness campaigns can encourage greater public engagement in science, including participation in citizen science projects, attendance at science festivals and public lectures, and involvement in science-related community initiatives. This engagement can foster a culture of curiosity and lifelong learning.

Bridging the Gap Between Research and Application: The Case Studies

Stanford Research Park (SRP)

Effective communication is crucial for ensuring that innovations and discoveries made in universities and research institutions are effectively translated into practical applications. This process involves not only the dissemination of research findings but also the articulation of their potential impact and applicability in real-world contexts. The case of Stanford Research Park (SRP) exemplifies this dynamic. The park has established itself as a leading model for translating academic research into commercial technologies, thereby playing a pivotal role in the development of Silicon Valley as a global innovation hub. Founded in 1951 as a collaboration between Stanford University and the city of Palo Alto, the park was designed to foster closer ties between academia and industry. By providing a physical space where university researchers and industry professionals could collaborate, the park facilitated the exchange of ideas and resources necessary for innovation.

One of the key elements of SRP's success has been its emphasis on effective communication. The park has implemented robust communication strategies to ensure that the cutting-edge research conducted at Stanford University is accessible and understandable to industry partners. This includes regular seminars, workshops, and networking events that bring together researchers, entrepreneurs, and investors. These initiatives not only highlight the latest scientific advancements but also demonstrate their potential applications in various industries, from information technology to biotechnology. Moreover, SRP has established dedicated communication offices that specialize in translating complex scientific concepts into language that is accessible to non-specialists. These offices work closely with researchers to create compelling narratives about their work, emphasizing its relevance and potential impact. This approach has been instrumental in attracting venture capital and industry investment, which are crucial for the commercialization of new technologies.

The success of SRP in translating academic research into commercial technologies has had a significant impact on the growth of Silicon Valley. The park has incubated numerous successful startups, many of which have grown into leading technology

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companies. For instance, companies like Hewlett-Packard and Google had their origins in the collaborative environment fostered by SRP. These companies have not only contributed to the economic growth of the region but have also set benchmarks for innovation and technological advancement globally.

Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Facilitating industrial innovation is a vital function of science communication, especially when research findings are successfully shared with industry professionals. This exchange can stimulate the creation of new products, processes, and services, thereby advancing technological progress and boosting economic growth. The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Innovation Ecosystem is an exemplary case, where, MIT emphasizes extensive public outreach through open lectures, hackathons, and collaboration with industry partners. The dedicated communication teams at MIT ensure that research outcomes are widely disseminated, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship. A notable example of this dynamic is the collaboration between the MIT and various biotech companies, which has led to significant advancements in medical technologies and pharmaceuticals. The partnership between MIT and the biotechnology sector illustrates how the effective communication of scientific research can drive industrial innovation.

The MIT's strategy includes a robust framework for disseminating research outcomes to industry stakeholders, encompassing both formal and informal channels. These efforts involve publishing research in esteemed scientific journals, presenting findings at industry conferences, and engaging in strategic partnerships with biotech firms. A cornerstone of MIT's success in fostering industrial innovation is the role of its Technology Licensing Office (TLO). The TLO identifies research with commercial potential, secures patents, and licenses technologies to industry partners. This office acts as a conduit between the academic and commercial spheres, ensuring that groundbreaking discoveries are communicated to and utilized by industry professionals to develop marketable products. The impact of MIT's collaborations with biotech companies is evidenced by numerous medical technologies and pharmaceutical innovations. For example, advanced drug delivery systems developed through these partnerships have revolutionized treatment methodologies for various diseases, including cancer, by enhancing drug efficacy and minimizing side effects. Additionally, the development of portable diagnostic devices and lab-on-a-chip technologies has significantly improved disease detection and monitoring, offering rapid, accurate results that facilitate early intervention and treatment, thus improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs.

In the field of regenerative medicine, MIT's research has propelled significant advancements in tissue engineering and stem cell therapy. These innovations offer promising new treatment options for conditions with limited or no effective therapies, demonstrating the far-reaching impact of effective science communication on industrial innovation. Moreover, the collaboration between MIT and the biotech industry has fostered a thriving ecosystem of innovation and entrepreneurship. This environ-

ment has led to the creation of numerous startups founded by MIT researchers and alumni, many of which have become leaders in the biotech industry. These startups not only commercialize MIT's research but also generate high-skilled jobs and contribute to regional economic development.

Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN)

The Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN) in the UK plays a pivotal role in facilitating the flow of knowledge and fostering collaboration among businesses, academia, and government organizations. Its primary objective is to bridge the gap between research institutions and industry, thereby promoting innovation and economic growth. KTN accomplishes this by organizing events, networking opportunities, and collaborative projects that connect stakeholders with complementary expertise, leading to joint research initiatives, technology development, and commercialization opportunities. Additionally, KTN supports technology transfer by offering guidance on intellectual property management, technology licensing, and commercialization strategies, ensuring that innovative ideas are transformed into market-ready products and services. By fostering a collaborative environment and providing access to funding opportunities and resources, KTN stimulates innovation across various sectors. The network also promotes best practices in innovation management and technology development, enhancing organizational capabilities and competitive advantage. Effective science communication is crucial for KTN as it boosts visibility and engagement, attracting stakeholders and reinforcing its role as a key facilitator of knowledge transfer and collaboration within the innovation ecosystem.

Science communication also facilitates better understanding among stakeholders regarding KTN's objectives and benefits, aligning interests and facilitating collaborative efforts. This improved communication supports the exchange of knowledge among network members and attracts additional funding and investment by demonstrating the tangible outcomes of KTN's programs and projects. For instance, KTN's collaboration with Innovate UK exemplifies the benefits of science communication, as it helps connect businesses with resources needed to develop and commercialize new technologies. Similarly, KTN's sector-specific initiatives, such as those focused on healthcare or digital technologies, benefit from targeted science communication that highlights relevant research advancements and industry needs. This targeted approach ensures that stakeholders are informed about the latest developments and opportunities within their specific sectors.

Current State of Science Communication in OIC Member Countries

Science communication within the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) member countries is undergoing significant development, with various initiatives designed to improve the dissemination and understanding of scientific knowledge. Several key aspects illustrate this evolving landscape: Firstly, the Science Communication Advisory Committee (SCAC), established by COMSTECH (the OIC's Standing Committee on Scientific and Technological Cooperation), plays a pivotal role in advancing science communication across member states. The SCAC is tasked with ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of science communication efforts. It provides strategic

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guidance, evaluates the impact of existing initiatives, and develops new programs to enhance the dissemination of scientific knowledge throughout the OIC region (Khurshid 2023). Secondly, international conferences and workshops, such as the COMSTECH International Conference on Science Communication and Community Engagement, serve as critical platforms for fostering dialogue among students, academicians, science communicators, and journalists. These events are instrumental in promoting science communication and facilitating the exchange of ideas and best practices.

Science communication in OIC member countries has made substantial strides, particularly in nations that have strategically prioritized science and technology as cornerstones of their development. Turkey, Iran, and Malaysia have emerged as leaders in this domain. Turkey has placed a strong emphasis on public engagement, fostering a robust connection between scientists and the general public. Iran has focused on disseminating research findings, particularly in engineering and medical sciences, to both academic and public audiences. Malaysia has heavily invested in STEM education and science communication initiatives, positioning itself as a regional leader. Saudi Arabia and Egypt have also made significant contributions, with Saudi Arabia prioritizing renewable energy and biotechnology through initiatives like the King Abdul-Aziz City for Science and Technology (KACST), while Egypt continues to leverage its rich scientific heritage to integrate science communication into public discourse. Countries such as Pakistan, the UAE, Qatar, Jordan, and Lebanon have advanced in specialized areas, ranging from biotechnology and environmental sciences to space exploration and science literacy, thereby contributing to a growing culture of scientific inquiry and public engagement across the region (Oldac 2022).

However, this progress is accompanied by diverse challenges and opportunities. The scientific capabilities and infrastructure among OIC member states vary significantly. While some countries possess advanced research facilities and vibrant scientific communities, others grapple with limited political will and inadequate funding mechanisms (Haq and Awan 2020). Addressing these disparities is critical for building supportive ecosystems that not only facilitate scientific research but also foster public acceptance of emerging technologies.

A key area of focus within the OIC is enhancing STEM education, with concerted efforts aimed at encouraging more students to pursue careers in these fields. This is seen as essential for cultivating a strong scientific community and driving innovation across the region. Additionally, agro-biotechnology has gained prominence, given the agriculture-based economies prevalent in many OIC countries. Although biotechnology holds the promise of improving agricultural productivity, the adoption of biotech crops remains uneven, with only a few member states officially cultivating them. As science communication continues to evolve, it will play a crucial role in bridging these gaps and advancing scientific progress across the OIC.

Strategies for Enhancing Science Communication in STPs

To enhance science communication within STPs, several strategic approaches can be employed to maximize the impact and effectiveness of communication efforts. First-

ly, developing comprehensive communication plans is essential. Such plans should detail the objectives of communication activities, identify target audiences, craft key messages, and select appropriate communication channels. A structured plan ensures that all communication efforts are aligned with the overarching goals of the STP, facilitating a coherent and strategic dissemination of information. This includes defining specific metrics for success and establishing a timeline for implementation, which helps in tracking progress and making necessary adjustments. Secondly, leveraging digital tools is a critical strategy for modern science communication. Utilizing social media platforms, websites, blogs, and other digital media enables STPs to reach a broad audience and engage with stakeholders in real-time. Digital tools offer the advantage of interactive and immediate communication, allowing for the dissemination of research findings, updates on ongoing projects, and insights into the activities of the STP. Effective use of these platforms also fosters community building and enhances the visibility of the STP's initiatives.

Implementing training programs is another key strategy. Providing researchers and entrepreneurs with training in science communication equips them with the skills needed to effectively convey their work to diverse audiences. This training should cover various aspects of communication, including public speaking, media interactions, and the use of visual aids. By enhancing these skills, researchers and entrepreneurs can better articulate the significance of their work, engage more effectively with stakeholders, and contribute to a more informed public discourse. Finally, promoting public engagement through events, workshops, and exhibitions is crucial for raising awareness about the activities and achievements of STPs. Such events serve as platforms for direct interaction between the public and scientific professionals, facilitating a deeper understanding of ongoing research and technological advancements. These engagements not only highlight the contributions of the STP but also foster public interest in science and technology, encouraging greater community involvement and support for the STP's initiatives.

A combination of these strategies—developing comprehensive communication plans, leveraging digital tools, implementing training programs, and promoting public engagement—can significantly enhance the effectiveness of science communication in STPs. By adopting these approaches, STPs can improve their ability to disseminate information, foster collaboration, and engage with various stakeholders, ultimately contributing to a more robust and dynamic innovation ecosystem.

Recommendations for OIC Member Countries

To enhance the effectiveness of science communication within STPs in OIC member countries, several strategic recommendations are proposed, few of them are as follows:

1. Investing in Communication Strategies: STP administrations should allocate resources towards the development and implementation of comprehensive communication strategies. These strategies must outline clear objectives, identify target audiences, articulate key messages, and specify communication channels. Such investments will ensure that science communication efforts are systematic, goal-oriented, and effective in disseminating scientific and technological advance-

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ments. This should also include the establishment of robust digital platforms, outreach programs, and public engagement activities to increase the visibility and impact of STPs.

2. **Supporting Initiatives by COMSTECH:** COMSTECH should enhance its role in promoting science communication across OIC member countries. COMSTECH can provide support through financial resources for various communication projects and events. Additionally, offering training programs to improve the communication skills of researchers, entrepreneurs, and science communicators will be beneficial. By supplying essential resources and expertise, COMSTECH can help standardize and elevate science communication practices within STPs across the OIC region.
3. **Conducting Further Research:** Further research is needed to develop and refine science communication approaches tailored to the unique contexts of OIC member countries. This research should focus on identifying regional challenges, cultural factors, and existing infrastructure to create customized communication strategies. By examining successful models and practices both within the OIC region and globally, stakeholders can adapt and implement best practices that address regional needs and resonate with diverse audiences.
4. **Encouraging Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** STPs should promote interdisciplinary collaboration by creating platforms for researchers from different fields to engage with each other. This can be achieved through joint research projects, conferences, and networking events that encourage the exchange of ideas and expertise. Such collaborations can enhance the quality and impact of scientific research and communication.
5. **Fostering Public Engagement:** STPs should organize public engagement initiatives such as science fairs, workshops, and open days to raise awareness about their activities and achievements. These events can help demystify scientific processes, showcase innovations, and foster a greater appreciation for science among the general public.
6. **Leveraging Digital Tools:** STPs should utilize digital platforms, including social media, websites, and blogs, to disseminate information and engage with a broader audience. Effective use of these tools can enhance the reach and impact of science communication efforts, making scientific knowledge more accessible and engaging.
7. **Developing a Science Communication Media Resource Kit:** To support and standardize science communication efforts, STPs should develop a Science Communication Media Resource Kit. This kit should include guidelines for creating effective science communication materials, templates for press releases and social media posts, and resources for training communicators. Such a kit will provide valuable tools and resources to ensure consistent and high-quality communication across different STPs and enhance the overall impact of science communication activities.

By implementing these recommendations, STPs in OIC member countries can significantly enhance their science communication, leading to greater public engagement, improved collaboration, and more effective dissemination of scientific and technological advancements.

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Pharmacovigilance Communication to Prevent Adverse Events in OIC Member States

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Abstract

Pharmacovigilance is crucial in ensuring public health and safety by monitoring and managing adverse events following immunization (AEFI). Effective communication is a vital component of pharmacovigilance, enabling the timely detection, assessment, and prevention of adverse events. The article emphasizes the need for accurate, trustworthy, and clear information, and highlights the role of graphic design, social media, and risk communication in pharmacovigilance. This article aims to promote best practices and enhance public health outcomes by exploring the challenges and opportunities in pharmacovigilance communication. Ultimately, effective communication in pharmacovigilance can save lives and prevent harm, making it an essential aspect of healthcare policy and practice Pharmacovigilance.

Keywords: Communication, Pharmacovigilance, Adverse Events, Public Health, Healthcare Policy, Medication Safety, OIC Member States

Introduction

Pharmacovigilance and effective communication are crucial components of ensuring public health and safety. This article will delve deeper into the importance of communication in pharmacovigilance, exploring the challenges, opportunities, and best practices in this field.

During 1957-61, the use of Thalidomide by pregnant mothers resulted in the biggest disaster in the Health System. Pregnant mothers born more than 10,000 children without limbs as well as miscarriages in 45 countries.

Marketing of Thalidomide by German Company

Thalidomide was introduced by German Pharmaceutical Company as a medication for anxiety, and as a sedative. Thalidomide initially seemed to be safe, concerns regarding birth defects were noted in 1961, and the medication was removed from the market in Europe at that time.

Who Suspected Birth Defects in Thalidomide?

In Australia, a midwife in Sydney first raised concerns both defects linked to thalidomide. German Pediatrician, who also suspected the link is credited with conducting scientific research that proved thalidomide was causing birth defects in 1961.

Of those pregnant mothers who took thalidomide on the prescription of the physician, born about 40 % in the death form or shortly after the time of birth. Its initial entry into the US market was prevented by the US Food & Drug Administration (FDA). The birth defects of Thalidomide led to the development of greater drug regulation and post-market surveillance in many countries like the USA.

In the UK, there were 429 Children with thalidomide-related disabilities till 1997, and the UK Government gave a grant of \$20 million to be distributed to the patients through the Thalidomide Trust in 2009. In Spain, thalidomide was widely available throughout 1970, and 1980. The reason was, that Spain's controls and safeguarding the patients were poor. The Spanish advocacy group of Thalidomide estimates that in 2015, there were 250 living victims of thalidomide in Spain.

In East Germany, thalidomide was rejected by the regulatory body and was never approved for use. There are no known thalidomide effected babies born in East Germany. In West Germany, approximately, 2,500 babies were born with birth defects from thalidomide. In the USA, the FDA refused approval to market thalidomide saying further studies were needed. The numerous reports of malformations in babies brought about the awareness of the side effects of the drugs on pregnant women. The birth defects caused by the drug thalidomide can range from moderate to more server forms. The disaster prompted many countries to introduce tougher rules for the testing and licensing of drugs. In the USA, with new regulations, the FDA requires applicants to prove efficacy and disclose all side effects encountered in testing.

In 2009, the Saudi Food and Drug Administration established the National Pharmacovigilance Center and became a member of the W.H.O. pharmacovigilance Program. The Pharmacovigilance Centre (PVC) of Iran began its activities under the supervision of the Iran Food and Administration) in 1991. It then became the full member of the WHO International Drug Monitoring in 1998.

Only 45% of Arab Countries are official Members of the WHO Collaborating Centre for international Drug Monitoring. Countries such as Morocco, Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Jordan are considered to be advanced Pharmacovigilance countries. Countries such as Somalia, Djibouti, and Mauritania have no or weak pharmacovigilance system.

History of Pharmacovigilance in Pakistan

First time in the history of Pakistan, Pharmacovigilance was enacted in the Drug Regulatory Authority Act, of 2012. The Pharmacovigilance Rules, 2022 were notified through S.R.O 540/202 after the approval of Federal Government.

- **The DRAP Structure:** DRAP consists of 13 Divisions and each Division has its own responsibility. Under Pharmacovigilance Rules, Pakistan National Pharmacovigilance Centre works under the Division of Pharmacy Service. Director, Division of Pharmacy Services of the DRAP is Head of the Pakistan National Pharmacovigilance Center. Centre has appropriate full-time technical staff, infrastructure and technical facility to perform the Pharmacovigilance activities.

Pharmacovigilance Communication...

- **National Pharmacovigilance Centre Role:** The NPC shall acquire national database and is linked to the World Health Organization Uppsala Monitoring Centre, Sweden (WHO-UMC), and with Provincial Pharmacovigilance Centre and Public Health Programs. Each Provincial government and administrative territory shall establish a provincial pharmacovigilance center under the respective Health Department for therapeutic goods safety monitoring and execution of pharmacovigilance activities. At each secondary and tertiary care public and private sector hospital, a pharmacovigilance center shall be established for reporting of ADR.
- **Evaluation and Risk Management by the DRAP:** The DRAP shall notify the Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Expert Committee (PRAEC) for risk management associated with the use of therapeutic goods i.e. signal detection, causality assessment, risk minimization, communication related to risk of adverse events and evaluation of periodic reports. The registration holder shall collect Adverse Drug Reports (ADR), AEFI, and Adverse Events and report to the National Pharmacovigilance Center for passive surveillance, active surveillance and post-authorization studies.
- **Med Safety Mobile APP:** The ADRs and AEFIs can be collected by using the latest technology like the Med Safety Mobile App, WhatsApp, messages, emails, phones or any other swift means. Division of Pharmacy Services also collects ADRs through Hard copies from Pharma Industry.

Pharmacovigilance during COVID and a Guide for Good Communication:

During COVID-19 more than 60150 AEFIs have been collected. All ADRs and AEFIs have been collected at the National Pharmacovigilance Centre, DRAP, and then submitted to WHO Uppsala Monitoring Centre Sweden.

Effective Communication in Pharmacovigilance

Pharmacovigilance communication is crucial for ensuring accurate and timely information exchange among healthcare professionals, patients, and stakeholders. Making sure our message gets through careful thought and planning. As pharmacovigilance is a new field in underdeveloped Muslim countries and need training and skills to communicate between doctor to doctor, doctor to the pharmacist, nurse to the pharmacist, and patient to the pharmacist. As in the use of medicines, the pharmacist is mainly responsible, so he is the custodian for medication safety and patient safety. There are some key principles of effective communication such as;

1. Accuracy, 2. Trustworthiness, 3. Clarity 4. Conciseness, 5. Cultural competence

Verbal Communication

1. Clear language, 2. Active listening, 3. Empathy, 4. Avoid jargon
5. Simple explanations

Non-Verbal Communication

1. Body language, 2. Tone of voice, 3. Eye contact, 4. Proximity, 5. Visual aids

Written Communication

1. Clear writing style, 2. Organized content, 3. Headings and subheadings
4. Bullet points, 5. Avoid ambiguity

Interpersonal Communication

1. Build trust, 2. Open dialogue, 3. Respect perspectives, 4. Encourage feedback
5. Address concerns

Technological Communication

1. Email, 2. Phone calls, 3. Video conferencing, 4. Social media, 5. Online forums

Effective Graphic Design for ADR Communication

Graphic design plays a vital role in conveying your message effectively during Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) communication. Well-designed visuals can enhance understanding, while poorly designed ones can confuse or mislead. To communicate successfully, consider the following essential tips:

Seven Key Principles of Graphic Design for ADR Communication

1. Consistency is Key: Establish a consistent visual identity across all channels. Select a style that works for you and use it uniformly.
2. Channel-Specific Design: Tailor your design to each platform. Posters and detailed infographics may not suit Twitter or Instagram, but excel on pages or presentations.
3. Modular Content: Break up content into bite-sized pieces for different channels, drawing your audience in.
4. Clear Typography: Choose one readable font and stick to it. Avoid cluttering images with excessive text, ensuring easy readability.
5. Simple Color Palette: Limit your colors to create visually appealing and digestible graphics.
6. Impactful Imagery: Select high-quality images that resonate with your audience and convey your message. Avoid using images as mere fillers.
7. Graphic Elements: Utilize icons and other visual elements to convey information concisely, going beyond photographs.

Additional Considerations

- Consider your target audience and adapt your design accordingly.
- Ensure consistency across social media platforms.
- Balance text and visuals for optimal engagement.

By incorporating these principles into your graphic design strategy, you'll effectively communicate your message and enhance understanding of ADRs.

Pharmacovigilance Communication...

A Guide to Risk Communication:

Risk Communication in Pharmacovigilance involves:

1. Disseminating accurate information
2. Raising awareness of potential health hazards
3. Encouraging informed decision-making

The following 6 Tips are important for Effective Risk Communication

1. Contextualize Risks: Go beyond numerical data.
2. Frame Risks with Benefits: Provide balanced information.
3. Listen to Your Audience: Understand concerns.
4. Use Visual Aids: Graphics facilitate understanding.
5. Address Uncertainties: Be transparent about unknowns.
6. Inform, Don't Persuade: Maintain objectivity.

Implementation and Evaluation

To ensure effective communication:

1. Develop a communication strategy.
2. Train healthcare professionals.
3. Conduct regular evaluations.
4. Gather feedback from stakeholders.
5. Continuously improve communication materials.

By incorporating these elements, principles, and strategies, pharmacovigilance communication can be optimized to ensure accurate, timely, and effective information exchange.

Future directions:

Pharmacovigilance Communication Strategies for OIC Member States

1. OIC Pharmacovigilance Network: Establish a network for collaboration and information sharing.
2. Harmonized Reporting: Implement harmonized adverse event reporting across member states.
3. Regional Training: Conduct regional training programs for healthcare professionals.
4. Patient Safety Initiatives: Promote patient safety initiatives and awareness campaigns
5. Regulatory Harmonization: Foster regulatory harmonization and cooperation.
6. Safety Alert System: Develop a system for sharing safety alerts and warnings.
7. Quarterly Newsletter: Publish a quarterly newsletter on pharmacovigilance activities.
8. Stakeholder Engagement: Engage with healthcare professionals, patients, and industry.
9. Public Awareness: Conduct public awareness programs on medication safety.

10. Collaboration with International Organizations: Collaborate with international organizations (e.g., WHO, Uppsala Monitoring Centre).
11. Capacity Building: Provide capacity-building programs for member states.
12. Pharmacovigilance Guidelines: Develop and share joint pharmacovigilance guidelines among OIC Member States.
13. Safety Data Sharing: Encourage sharing of safety data and best practices.
14. Regional Pharmacovigilance Centers: Establish regional pharmacovigilance centers.
15. OIC Pharmacovigilance Day: Celebrate OIC Pharmacovigilance Day to raise awareness.

By implementing these strategies, OIC member states can enhance pharmacovigilance communication, ensuring safe and effective medication use across the regions.

Conclusion:

This article highlighted how the drug regulatory system of the drugs was created globally to protect and safeguard patients. There is a dire need for Muslim Ummah shall establish a joint OIC Member States Pharmacovigilance Centre. Future directions and quick guides to reduce risk during communication have been given to each Muslim state to prevent adverse events.

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Science Diplomacy and Vaccine Nationalism: A Proposal for Pakistan's Vaccine Development Complex

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Abstract

Science diplomacy (SD) is an initiative to solve the challenges emanating from non-traditional security. These challenges impact the whole international community and must be coped with joint efforts. Scientific and technological progress brought nations together and the spread of technologies and technological cooperation among nations upgraded the overall living standard of people. The study focuses on the political side of technology transfer as part of vaccine nationalism; big powers have either tried to control or limit the transfer of technology. The strict technology transfer regimes are the watchdogs that make sure that technology remains in the hands of few. In the case of Covid-19, many states who were manufacturing vaccines in large numbers refused to provide those to other developing countries. In the same context, Pakistan has also been facing a discriminatory approach and preferential treatment by Western countries. Pakistan has been suffering from most viruses throughout history including polio, Dengue, Chikungunya, Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic fever and pandemics like COVID-19, but always got vaccines that served the interest of first-world countries. The study proposed that keeping in view the nationalist policies of Western countries, there is a dire need to develop a vaccine development complex in Pakistan to deal with all viruses and upcoming future pandemics.

Keywords: Science Diplomacy, Vaccine Diplomacy, Vaccine Nationalism, Non-Traditional Security Challenges, Vaccine Development Mechanism for Pakistan, Covid-19

Introduction

Scientific cooperation for the promotion of international relations is an old practice among nations. In ancient times monarchs would send their skilled workers to allies for their assistance in different fields, including architecture, agriculture, shipbuilding, medicine, etc. The Industrial Revolution expedited the process of scientific and technological development. People benefited from such advancements; several diseases, that killed hundreds and thousands of people in the past, became extinct after the development of vaccines and antibiotics. Connectivity increased; with the invention of the steam engine, which led to the invention of automobiles, trains, and airplanes; distances were reduced and transportation of goods was expedited.

There is a political side to technology and the transfer of technology; big powers have either tried to control or limit the transfer of technology. The strict technology transfer regimes are the watchdogs that make sure that technology remains in the hands of few. The politicization of health and medicine by big powers including tight control on drug manufacturing, supply, and sharing of technology causes millions of preventable deaths around the world. Pakistan has been suffering from most viruses throughout history including polio, Dengue, Chikungunya, Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic fever, and pandemics like COVID-19, but always got vaccines once they severed the interest of first world countries. The study focuses on what existing mechanisms for international cooperation in vaccine development can be leveraged by Pakistan and How can knowledge sharing and innovative solutions through SD contribute to Pakistan's self-sufficiency in vaccine production.

The research paper hypothesizes that increased engagement in SD will positively impact Pakistan's self-sufficiency in vaccine production and distribution. Pakistan needs to explore the options available to it which would make it self-sufficient in the health sector in general and vaccine development in particular. The spread of COVID-19 and the global response has resulted not only in the loss of human lives but also in economic and social implications. The pandemic exposed weaknesses of the international health system, let alone developing world, hospitals in developed nations were unable to cater to the number of patients they received.

Early cases of Covid-19 were detected in Pakistan in February 2020. The government was quick to respond and measures to contain the spread of disease were taken. Nonetheless, like any pandemic, several thousand people lost their lives. It exposed the vulnerabilities of Pakistan's health system. COVID-19 and the challenges faced by Pakistan in terms of the acquisition of vaccines is a wake-up call for the country. This further intensifies the need for a functional SD platform that focuses, among other fields, on health security. Medicine which cures the disease is important but vaccines are more important as they protect the whole society from a particular disease.

This study is qualitative in nature which aims to explore options available to Pakistan for cooperation in vaccine development. To understand the mechanism of such cooperation, existing cooperation mechanisms are being discussed as a case study.

Conceptualizing Science Diplomacy

SD plays a crucial role in the foreign policy of the states. Whenever states come to the negotiation table for crisis management of fisheries, Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), territorial borders and space areas, they need scientists to help them in clear measurements in forming treaties and agreements. SD is a 19th-century concept when the World suffered from different infectious diseases, found gaps in knowledge and human curiosity to know about the world and led countries to engage in SD. However, it caught international attention when the Center for SD by the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) and the Royal Society jointly organized a conference titled New Frontiers of Science Diplomacy in 2009 that persuaded states to cooperate in SD. The conference provided three-dimensional definitions of SD:

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Science in Diplomacy, Science for Diplomacy and diplomacy for science. Norman Neureiter penned the first time on SD and defined it as, “An intentional effort to engage with other countries where the relationship is not good otherwise”.

SD engaged states with each other through diplomatic channels to enhance cooperation in Science and technology for the better good of society. According to Vaughan Turekian, Director of AAAS, Center for Science and Diplomacy, “The use and application of science cooperation to help build bridges and enhance relationships between and amongst societies, with a particular interest in working in areas where there might not be other mechanisms for an engagement at an official level”.

The concept of Diplomacy for Science or Science for Diplomacy got more prominence as its best includes the establishment of many International Research Centers that were jointly established by states to further promote diplomacy for science and exploration of new areas. In 2020, the European Union launched the European SD Alliance under the Horizon 2020 project aiming to advise SD stakeholders, nurture science, technology and innovation diplomacy and engage in project coordination and information exchanges. This alliance also opened space for other continents as they conducted a webinar with the African Union to discuss the future cooperation in SD between both regional organizations.

European countries launched three projects of SD funded by EU Horizon 2020 under the theme of Societal Challenges: Europe in a Changing World – Inclusive, Innovation and Reflective Societies. These projects include (i) ‘European Leadership in Cultural, Science and Innovation Diplomacy (EL-CSID); (ii) Using Science For/In Diplomacy for Addressing Global Challenges (S4D4C); and (iii) Inventing a Shared Science Diplomacy for Europe (InsSciDE).

EL-CSID was established in 2016 and continued till 2019. The project sought to understand the EU’s cultural, science and innovation diplomacy and its scope for enhancing its interests by creating awareness among stakeholders. They published research and policy publications and organized lectures, workshops, and conferences. It laid the foundation for the conceptualization of science and cultural diplomacy and sought to understand SD actors in the EU as well as collected evidence and provided recommendations for the EU’s science and cultural diplomacy. InSciDE aims to create an inclusive and innovative dialogue, highlighting the contribution of Science academies and networks of science diplomats to addressing global challenges. InsSciDE offers a framework for understanding and delivers stakeholder-supported strategy and policy recommendations”.

Besides this, Using Science for/in Diplomacy for Addressing Global Challenges (S4D4C) was established between 2018 to 2021. It was developed to support European SD as per their capacity. It analyzed and published about twenty-three case studies and policy briefs. S4D4C created an online course on SD in 2020. It was signed up by about 6000 individuals, of which 51 percent were female and included civil services officials, diplomats, science advisers, science administrators and scientists with or without any diplomatic responsibilities. S4D4C has also enabled networking

globally and fostered an SD community through training, workshops, webinars, and networking meetings, etc.

Other SD efforts include the establishment of the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) which is a collaboration of scientists, engineers, politicians and diplomats based in southern France. It is the world's largest scientific experiment to demonstrate the possibility of producing commercial energy from nuclear fusion launched in 1985. Where China, Russia, the US, Japan, South Korea, the EU and India are engaged in SD in one or another forum. It is very productive in the growth of the global fusion community resulting in cross-cultural scientific knowledge exchange.

Similarly, ICPT (The Abdul-Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics), is Italy-based International research center for physical and Mathematical Sciences that was founded in 1964. It operates under the tripartite agreement between the Italian Government, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). The Centre has the mandate to provide scientific expertise to developing countries with continuing education and skills. ICTP has been a major force in stemming the scientific brain drain from the developing world.

Furthermore, European Center for Nuclear Research (CERN) is a research organization that operates the largest particle physics laboratory in the world. It was founded in 1954 having 23 member states along with thousands of scientists worldwide. Along with this, the International Institute of Applied System Analysis (IIASA), an Austria-based institute, was founded in 1972. The institute produces policy-oriented research focusing on climate change, energy security and sustainable development. On the same agenda of research, 400 researchers from 52 countries are working and presenting the best example of SD.

In addition, SD transforming International order where scientists are playing their neutral role in mitigating the crisis and leading to crisis management. In 1987, a collaboration between scientists and diplomats against the Chemicals-affecting depletion of the Ozone layer led to the formation of the Montreal Protocol. Which ended the use of Ozone depletion substances in cars, fridges, and Air-Conditioners. That was the most significant achievement of SD.

Vaccine Diplomacy to Vaccine Nationalism

Vaccine diplomacy is essentially the manipulation of vaccines as a strategic tool for using vaccine development, production, and distribution to strengthen ties between nations and enhance global health security, and otherwise produce goodwill. Essentially, it concerns cooperation between nations that provide access to vaccines, especially in such a health crisis situation like the COVID-19 pandemic. While vaccine diplomacy responds to the more general public health interests of a country, it also brings a nation political influence in that its scientific might is observable and it has committed humanitarian services. It can then mitigate or nullify vaccine nationalism; that is, equal vaccination access, primarily for low- and middle-income countries, can be achieved to stabilize the world.

Science Diplomacy and Vaccine Nationalism...

Vaccine nationalism refers to the precedence given to citizens of the country in receiving vaccines during health crisis-related circumstances. Vaccine nationalism has its roots in some historical events where countries prioritized their domestic needs over others during pandemics or outbreaks. Some of the earliest examples can be drawn from the 20th-century smallpox eradication efforts. Countries prioritized their populations, leading to unequal access for developing nations. The HIV/AIDS crisis in the late 1980s and early 1990s highlighted vaccine nationalism as wealthier nations hoarded resources while poorer countries struggled to access essential treatments and preventive measures. The 2009 H1N1 pandemic exacerbated the issue, with countries rushing to secure vaccine supplies for their populations. Many high-income nations purchased doses far exceeding their needs, leaving low-income countries with limited access.

Vaccine nationalism was observed currently in early 2020 during COVID-19 when the US pre-purchased 100 million doses of vaccine from the Sanofi-GSK collaboration for its “Operation Warp Speed” to eradicate coronavirus from the US first. The US blocked the export of raw materials for vaccine production by invoking the Defense Production Act. The Act curbed the import of Bioreactor bags, filters and cell culture media which is critical for vaccine development. The then CEO of Serum Institute of India (SII) and Bharat Biotech requested the USA to lift the embargo that was negatively affecting the vaccine production companies of India. Similarly, the UK pre-invested in the Oxford University vaccine development program. EU joined the race by approving a stimulus package of \$USD 857 for grants and loans. Canada was involved in this race by buying a very large number of vaccines that were more than needed.

The vaccine inequity becomes very evident when countries/regions like the European Union (EU) has vaccinated about 55.8%; the UK - 68.3%; Spain - 63.5%; Canada - 70%; whereas on the other hand, the developing countries are in a very critical situation. The 16 rich countries representing only 14% of the world’s population had pre-ordered more than 53% of the potential vaccine doses. Moreover, the major exporters have mainly developed countries such as Germany (\$84.7 bn), Switzerland (\$71.7 bn), the US (\$49.7 bn), Belgium (\$45.7 bn) and Ireland (\$40 bn). Concomitantly, these countries are also the only major importers, with the US (\$99.7 bn), Germany (\$53.7 bn), Belgium (\$36.7 bn), United Kingdom (\$33.8 bn), and Switzerland (\$29.3 bn)

New Delhi developed its COVID-19 vaccine namely COVAXIN produced by Bharat Biotech with the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) in collaboration with the National Institute of Virology. According to the Journal for Travel Medicine, the Serum Institute of India (SII) is the world’s largest vaccine producer and leading export of vaccines. SII (Covishield, Covovax, and COVI-VAC), Bharat Biotech (BBV154), Dr. Reddy’s Laboratories (Sputnik V), Biological E Limited (Janssen Ad26.COVS.2 and Bio E COVID-19), Aurobindo Pharma (UB-612), and Indian Immunologicals (Live attenuated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine developed by Griffith University) all of these have a license to develop the vaccine. It is important to note that India also followed the path of vaccine nationalism and provided its vaccines to all South Asian states (except Pakistan) to most of the African states, Caribbean community states, Middle

Eastern states, and also to UN peace-keeping missions under the “Vaccine Maitri” project.

States used vaccine diplomacy to enhance their power internationally. According to the Australian Research Group, Lowy’s Asian Power & Diplomacy Program, the US enhanced its power in Asia more than China and left Beijing second. It is the first time that the Research Institute added vaccine diplomacy to measure the power of the states. As per the study of the group, the top 10 countries for overall power in the Asia-Pacific region are the US, China, Japan, India, Russia, Australia, South Korea, Singapore, Indonesia and Thailand. The ranking this year reflected the longer-term impact of the pandemic, with the overall power of most countries falling compared to last year in the index. Although, the US was the late-comer in Latin America in terms of vaccine diplomacy as it commenced vaccine diplomacy in June 2021 followed by Russia in February 2021, and China in March 2021. But after coming into the competition the US became the biggest vaccine provider to Latin American states.

Wilson Center also confirmed American vaccine diplomacy’s edge over China and Russia, they underscored that the US distributed vaccines to Colombia (63%), Peru (54%), Brazil (43%), Argentina (35%) and Mexico (17%) as compared to Chinese distribution to Colombia (16%), Peru (9%), Brazil (18%), Argentina (26%) and Mexico (33%). Apart from the US, China also pledged to provide Vaccines to 80 countries under the Health Silk Road Initiative. Importantly, According to the Think Global Health report April 2021, among 56 countries to which China pledges doses, 55 are members of its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) project. to enhance Beijing’s soft power image.

Pakistan’s Vaccine Development Gap: A Road to Self-Reliance

Pakistan is importing all sorts of vaccines for immunization in response to public health needs, placing high emphasis on immunization programs as well as sometimes on response programs to infectious diseases. The vaccines include the polio vaccine made up of inactivated poliovirus vaccine, IPV and oral poliovirus vaccine, OPV. The country still endeavors to eradicate polio worldwide. This not only involves the importation of the Measles, Mumps, and Rubella vaccines to prevent any outbreaks of these diseases but also hepatitis A and hepatitis B vaccines to curb the high levels of hepatitis that also prevail in this region. The diphtheria, Tetanus, and Pertussis combination vaccine is another very essential immunizing agent against which the children need to be protected and has been scheduled in the national immunization schedule. Vaccines that are being imported include Sinopharm, Sinovac, AstraZeneca, and Pfizer-BioNTech, as Pakistan vaccinated its population during the COVID-19 pandemic. Imported seasonal influenza vaccines have also been applied in an attempt to reduce cases of flu among vulnerable groups. Typhoid, meningitis, and rabies vaccines are introduced based on priorities and outbreak situations. Whereas most of the above imports come from established manufacturers and world health organizations, bolstering the nation’s ability to produce a vaccine may mitigate reliance upon foreign supplies in the long run.

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Pakistan has been suffering from most viruses throughout history. Polio was seen as a disease in the early 1950s and 1960s and the World developed its vaccine by adopting the Global Polio Eradication Initiative in 1988. The Polio vaccine was effective and saved the lives of millions of children. But again when it accomplished the needs of the first world, transferred it to third-world states like Pakistan. Therefore, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Nigeria are the states that still have cases of Polio. Polio is one of the most viral diseases that staunched its stems in Pakistan during the 1990s. It was countered by launching the Pakistan Polio Eradication Program in 1994 a public-private partnership supported by WHO, UNICEF, and the Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI). National Immunization Days (NID) are set to vaccinate 40 million children across Pakistan and 33 million are fully polio-vaccinated. Pakistan's efforts found fruitful results as only one case of polio was registered during 2021. Conversely, Pakistan's initiatives for Polio eradication were funded by the World Bank where Pakistan relied on foreign countries to supply polio vaccines.

Along with Polio, Pakistan has suffered a lot of viruses i.e. Dengue, Chikungunya, Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic fever, and many more. The government's drive against chikungunya was and remains primarily focused on spraying for the Aedes mosquito vector, but filth and garbage around the buildings, including the provincial government hospital, as well as streets and roadsides, were not removed. Dengue Vaccines are not available in Pakistan. It is important to note that Pakistan has Extended Programme Immunisation (EPI) launched in 1978; which aims to protect children by immunizing them against tuberculosis, poliomyelitis, diphtheria, pertussis, tetanus, and measles. The program aims to vaccinate children aged 0-15. But ironically these immunization vaccines are being imported by multinational manufacturers and assisted by WHO, GAVI, and UNICEF.

Apart from these diseases, Pakistan suffered a lot due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The first case of COVID-19 was seen in Karachi in February 2020 followed by four waves of COVID-19. The first wave (March 2020-June 2020), Second wave (Nov-Dec 2020), third wave (March-April 2021), and fourth wave (May-August 2021), and now according to the Pakistan Government estimation fifth wave can be possible. In the fourth wave of COVID-19, as of now, Pakistan has lost 28,777 people and cases are not being reported yet.

Pakistan's economy, education, health sector, and the masses suffered a lot. Government steps to secure the border first policy led them to suspend the intra-city transportation that generated joblessness and crisis. Similarly, Daily wage labor is affected most due to COVID-19. Because in the initial stage of the emergence of COVID-19 government inflicted the complete lock down technique. According to the Pakistan Institute of Development Economics Report 2020, It is estimated that poverty could be increased by 58% due to COVID-19. The Pakistan stock market lost an average of 1500 points daily, in the commencing days of lock down in March 2020. By focusing on all of the challenges Pakistan pioneered a Smart lock down policy where working hours were restricted to some time. On an educational front, it is alarming to note that 42 million school-going children (from pre-primary, and primary, to higher secondary

and degree college levels) were unable to take regular classes. In addition, the Private sector failed to pay salaries to the teachers as students were unable to afford the high salaries. In a report released in 2020, the World Bank anticipated that 930,000 children would drop out of elementary and secondary school in Pakistan. In addition, the report states that we foresee the biggest (number of) dropouts in Pakistan as a result of the COVID situation.

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), Pakistan has 48 million impact learners because of the COVID-19 pandemic, out of which 1.9 million are enrolled at the tertiary level. Although Pakistan has developed its local vaccine PakVac in collaboration with China and also produces Chinese vaccines CansinoBio. In response to all of these efforts, Pakistan had no basic facilities to diagnose the virus and relied on China, Japan, and the Netherlands to test the samples. The government gets diagnostic kits from China and primers from Japan to diagnose the virus which delayed the process of vaccination. In the domain of vaccine development, Pakistan is still receiving Chinese and American-made vaccines in which Sinopharm, Sinovac, Cansino, Moderna, Pfizer, and AstraZeneca are included under international COVAX arrangements and bilateral agreements with China. International organizations like the World Bank and UNICEF are supporting Islamabad. In April 2021, the World Bank approved the Pandemic Response Effectiveness in Pakistan Project (PREPP) and redeployed \$153 million in support of Pakistan's vaccine drives.

Pakistan founded Quarantine centers in Karachi, Lahore and the City of Taftan (along with Pakistan-Iran Borders) under the National Action Plan for the Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) Pakistan. The purpose of this plan was to devise policies and a template to help provincial governments and states across Pakistan with a guide for them to develop methods and strategies to best deal with the COVID-19 outbreak. But still, Pakistan does not have vaccine development mechanisms.

Vaccine Development Mechanism

At the international level, the vaccine development complex is available in the form of state-to-state cooperation or through multinational companies. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the vaccine development mechanism is divided into six steps. Pre-clinical studies, in which vaccine is tested in animals for checking safety and efficacy. In the phase I clinical trial, which vaccine is applied to healthy adults who volunteer themselves. In phase II clinical trial, the vaccine is given to people who have characteristics (such as age and physical health) similar to those for whom the new vaccine is intended.

Phase III Clinical trial, in which the vaccine is given to thousands of people. In phase IV post-marketing surveillance, the vaccine is approved and licensed, to monitor adverse events and to study long-term effects of the vaccine in the population. The last one is Human Challenge studies, in which a vaccine is given followed by the pathogen against which the vaccine is designed to protect. Such trials are uncommon in people as they present considerable ethical challenges. By considering these vital steps, some states have developed their vaccine and some are in a way.

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By focusing on the criteria of WHO, states are developing their vaccines. Taiwan produced its vaccine namely Medigen that was approved for emergency purposes on 19 July 2021. According to the Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunization GAVI, “A phase 4 clinical trial started on 7 October 2021 to measure the anti-SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibody titers in adult participants to demonstrate the immunogenicity and safety of a third–booster dose with Medigen’s COVID-19 vaccine. with Medigen’s COVID-19 vaccine.”

Moderna Vaccine also known as Spikevax is produced by the US and funded by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Disease (NIAID). It has completed its four phases and the US authorized its use for people aged 18 and older. The AstraZeneca/ University of Oxford was developed in the United Kingdom. Its use is authorized by the European Medicines Agency and WHO. The vaccine was also tested in India, Brazil, and Africa. Same like this, the SINOVA COVID-19 vaccine was developed by China and conducted a phase 3 trial in Brazil, Turkey, and Indonesia.

International cooperation for vaccine development can be seen during the COVID-19 pandemic such as collaboration between Russia, South Korea, and the EU in the development of Sputnik V to enhance the manufacturing capabilities. Various companies and research groups around the world are aiming to develop an effective plant-based COVID-19 vaccine to fight against this pandemic.

Each of these companies and research group demonstrated their innovations in developing vaccines based on their previous studies. iBio, a company in Texas, USA, is famous for Fast pharming systems and is a global leader in plant-based biologics manufacturing. Similarly, CC Pharming is a Beijing-based company focusing on the use of plant bioreactors for the development of animal-free, safe, high-value recombinant protein and peptide products for industrial and clinical applications. iBio and CC Pharming have been jointly working on a various project since 2018. The existing collaboration led both companies to the development of purely plant-based bioreactor technology having VLP technology. VLP technology which is synthesized to be a non-harmful material to human beings, can induce the human immune system by producing proteins and antigens that resemble the actual viral peptides. Pfizer and BioNTech also co-developed the COVID-19 vaccine namely Pfizer/BioNTech in December 2020. Pfizer is an American multinational, Pharmaceutical and biotechnology Corporation headquartered in New York. Whereas, BioNTech is a German biotechnology company.

Proposal of Vaccine Development Complex in Pakistan

Pakistan is a developing country that has relied on other states in the domain of science and technology which left Pakistan behind in the vaccine development complex. However, the COVID-19 pandemic led states to come up with vaccine development mechanisms. Vaccines in Pakistan can be produced by raw materials i.e., production sharing or basic manufacturing. The proposal is enumerated below:

Vaccine Development through Production Sharing

In the production-sharing category, Pakistan can develop its vaccine through two means including through state-to-state cooperation or its collaboration with The De-

veloping Countries Vaccine Manufacturers Network (DCVMN). For state-to-state cooperation, China, Brazil, Cuba and Vietnam are producing and supplying the vaccine to other countries, which can be the opportunity to be availed by Pakistan. China one of the leading manufacturers of vaccines has already collaborated with Pakistan during the COVID-19 pandemic, providing vaccines and expertise. China can offer technology transfer, training, and investment in local vaccine manufacturing facilities.

Back in July 2021, Cuba offered to establish a center for vaccine production in Pakistan which can be used for both indigenous use and exports. Ambassador of Cuba Zener Javier Caro Gonzalez proposed this during his meeting with the Federal Minister for Science and Technology. On 11 April 2024, The Brazilian Ministry of Health (MoH) and Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance have signed a landmark Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) to collaborate on vaccine production, innovation and global access. The same initiative can be taken by Pakistan to establish its vaccine development mechanism.

The Developing Countries Vaccine Manufacturers Network (DCVMN) affinity group can be used for vaccine production. The technical as well as operational capacity building is the key focus area of DCVMN, which tries to enhance the technical as well as operational capacities of vaccine manufacturers. So, through training programs, workshops, and technical assistance, the network tries to enhance production processes, quality control, and regulatory compliance for Pakistani manufacturers. DCVMN serves as a collaborative platform between the vaccine manufacturers, researchers, and policymakers of developing countries. It may result in partnerships and knowledge about vaccine development by Pakistani stakeholders from lessons learned from other countries while building best practices.

DCVMN advocates the cause of developing country manufacturers at international platforms so that through that effort, policies are decided that can benefit equitable access to vaccines and support local production. Through this advocacy, Pakistan can also avail favorable conditions for vaccine manufacturing ventures. The DCVMN can facilitate a linkage of Pakistani manufacturers with the world's experts at research institutes. Such linkages will result in collaborative research works, knowledge of technologies available globally, and support needed to develop specific new vaccines tailored to the health needs of Pakistan. DCVMN can assist in the identification of market acceptability for locally manufactured vaccines, and understand the dynamics of the global vaccine market to ensure easier entry into local as well as international markets.

Vaccine Development through Basic Manufacturing

For Basis manufacturing, the National Institute of Health (NIH) is another reputable research body in the area of public health, which can play its central role. The institute serves as the research and development division of NHS and a WHO collaborating center for viral diagnostics. Its Bio Products Division (BPD) manufactures bacterial and viral vaccines and therapeutic antisera. Vaccines are manufactured from both raw material (Basic Manufacturing) & Production Sharing i.e. Bulk Concentrates are pur-

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chased and processed for filling and packing into final containers. The Manufacturing of quality vaccines and anti-sera is carried out by the Biological Production Division (BPD) of NIH. BPD has five production units namely: (i) Measles Vaccine Production Laboratory; (ii) Tetanus Toxoid Production Laboratory; (iii) Cell Culture Rabies Vaccine Production Laboratory; (iv) Allergy Vaccine Production Laboratory; and (v) Typhoid & Cholera Vaccine Production Laboratory. The above-listed laboratories manufacture enumerating nine products by way of basic and shared manufacturing technology. (i) Measles vaccine; (ii) Tetanus Toxoid; (iii) Cell Culture rabies vaccine; (iv) Allergy vaccine; (v) Typhoid vaccine; (vi) Typhoid & Cholera vaccine; (vii) Anti-snake venom serum (polyvalent); (viii) Anti- snake venom serum (trivalent); and (ix) Anti- rabies serum (ARS).

Although the NIH has a specific demand to fulfill the vaccine requirements of the country, nearly all public sector demands are being met through imports from multinational manufacturers. The NIH has been fulfilling a portion of national needs and eventually period admissions can be refined for mass Production and export of Vaccines in other regions as well. The state of Pakistan has to prepare the scientists and researchers according to the guidelines of WHO; invest in human resource development also cooperation from private and public pharmaceutical industry can play a pivotal role in vaccine development.

Pakistan has many other such institutions, including the Centre of Excellence in Molecular Biology (CEMB), that are engaged in research on vaccine development by applying methods of production sharing and basic manufacturing or raw materials. Previously, the team of researchers at Dow University already formed therapeutic bio products called Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG) using plasma from a coronavirus-recovered patient to test victims and diagnose COVID-19. None of the vaccine production systems are comprehensive but disembodied. Pakistan has six veterinary research institutes located in Karachi, Lahore, Quetta, Peshawar Faisalabad and Rawalpindi so the production of 95 percent animal vaccines is going on locally by these private sectors which benefits the economy of the state. They are importing the vaccine for humans. Therefore, creating vaccines should be of great priority in a world where new and old diseases pose a threat to human existence.

Options for Pakistan

1. Pakistan should set out its goal to develop its vaccine development complex with the help of regional states such as Russia and China.
2. To achieve self-sufficiency in vaccine development, Pakistan requires the transfer of resources, infrastructure perturbation and technical assistance. Under technology transfer, Cuba has offered to assist Pakistan in establishing a Vaccine Production Center that would provide them with the technology needed for domestic use and for export as well.
3. Lack of vaccine development resources delayed the process of vaccination in Pakistan. China, globally stressing upon Intellectual property waiver. That can be

utilized by Pakistan. In this domain, Pakistan can establish a Vaccine Laboratory Network in all main cities having a center in the Capital under the administration of the National Institute of Health (NIH). Outstanding scientists from all over Pakistan and China will be chosen to work with the China-Pakistan Joint Vaccine Development Complex.

4. On the Regional level, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) could be utilized for the establishment of the Regional Vaccine Development Center. SCO consists of three vaccine producer states China, Russia, and India. The areas in which scientists of the SCO member states can cooperate on vaccine development.
5. Vaccine Development Centers could be established in different universities. Where courses on vaccine production in affiliation with foreign universities should be taught. Likewise, Vaccine and Viral Immunology offer courses in collaboration with Harvard Medical School Facility about cutting-edge development in the creation of vaccines to protect against viral infections. The Ministry of Science and Technology of Pakistan can play its crucial role by sending Pakistani students of Science and Medical on scholarships abroad including European and American states to attend certificate courses on the development of vaccines.
6. World-leading organizations are holding multilateral Leaders Task Forces to provide vaccines to the developing world. These organizations can collaborate in vaccine development mechanisms to which scientists from Pakistan could contribute.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the growing importance of SD particularly in the context of global health, highlights the critical role of international cooperation in addressing shared non-traditional challenges such as pandemics. Vaccine diplomacy, as an aspect of SD, has proven to be a powerful tool in fostering collaboration, enhancing public health security and building goodwill between nations. However, the COVID-19 pandemic also exposed the stark reality of vaccine nationalism, where wealthier nations secured the majority of vaccine supplies, leaving developing countries vulnerable. This inequitable distribution underscores the need for countries like Pakistan to build self-sufficiency in vaccine development. Given the historical and recent examples of vaccine nationalism, it is evident that relying on external sources for vaccines leaves countries at a disadvantage during global crises.

For Pakistan, establishing its own vaccine complex is not just a matter of health security but a strategic imperative to ensure timely access to life-saving vaccines. The study proposes to develop a vaccine development mechanism in Pakistan through production sharing and basic manufacturing. In production sharing, Pakistan can utilize its close partnership with China for technology and knowledge sharing for the development of vaccine development complex. Moreover, Cuba also offered Pakistan technology for vaccine development that Islamabad must utilize. In the same context, Pakistan must cooperate with DCVMN, which enhances the technical as well as op-

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erational capacities of vaccine manufacturers. Similarly, Brazil and GAVI signed an MoU to collaborate on vaccine production, innovation and global access. The same MoU can be signed between Pakistan and GAVI. With regards to, Basic manufacturing, NIH should play its pivotal role as the center of vaccine development complex of Pakistan. By investing in local research, strengthening manufacturing capacity, and engaging in SD, Pakistan can reduce its dependence on external sources and be better prepared to face future diseases and pandemics. This approach will also position the country as a key player in global health, contributing to regional and international efforts to ensure equitable access to vaccines and improved public health outcomes.

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